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Artificial Intelligence for Earth Observation Data Analysis

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Introduction

INTRODUCTION TO MACHINE LEARNING

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- Objectives:
 - Recall what you may already know
 - Get familiar with vocabulary
 - Be prepared for the rest of the technical lectures and practical work

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Machine Learning

- What does ML cover ?

I. INTRODUCTION

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Machine Learning

- What does ML cover ? Part of Artificial Intelligence

https://www.nerdm.com/2client=brz-moz&images© Josiane.Mothe@irit.fr (09 Avril 2021)

Machine Learning

- What does ML cover ? Part of Artificial Intelligence

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Machine Learning

- > Volume
- > Variety
- > Velocity
- > Veracity

- Information extraction,
- Data cleaning, augmentation

- Measures
- Graphs
- Synthetic views

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Machine learning

Wikipedia

Machine learning (ML) is the study of computer **algorithms** that improve automatically through experience and by the use of data. It is seen as a part of **artificial intelligence**. Machine learning algorithms build a model based on sample data, known as "**training data**", in order to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed to do so.

Data analytics

Wikipedia

Data analysis, also known as **analysis of data** or **data analytics**, is a process of inspecting, **cleansing**, **transforming**, and **modeling data** with the goal of discovering useful information, suggesting conclusions, and supporting decision-making. Data analysis has multiple facets and approaches, encompassing diverse techniques under a variety of names, in different business, science, and social science domains.

Big data Data representation

Data analysis
Data mining
Pattern extraction

Data visualisation
Interpretation
Results

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II. APPLICATIONS AND MAIN PRINCIPLES

Applications for machine learning

Images

https://www.wizaly.fr/blog/data-science-intelligence-artificielle/machine-learning-quelles-applications/?wiz_source=google&wiz_medium=cpc&wiz_campaign=wizaly_non_brand_2021&wiz_term=&wiz_content=128976938096&wiz_ad=CjwKCAjwsMGYBhAEIwAGUXJaX47QkJ0uVbikz69KYL8YR3yqVVeOFip7NdtUICPHjv8zv3t3S1YBGG9e8QAwE

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Applications for machine learning

Images and captions

Captioned by Human and by Google's Experimental Program

Human: "A group of men playing Frisbee in the park."
 Computer model: "A group of young people playing a game of Frisbee."

Applications for machine learning

- Medical images – cancer detection

UNIVERSITÉ DE JEAN JAURES Cancer Healthy © Josiane.Mothe@irit.fr

Applications for machine learning

- Images and security

Applications for machine learning

- Automatically generated images

Portrait Edmond de Belamy

« First » piece of artwork produced by artificial intelligence.

Sold for \$432,500 at Christie's on 25 October 2018

Work by the Obvious collective, made up of Hugo Caselles-Dupré, Pierre Fautrel et Gauthier Vernier (French).

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Applications for machine learning

- Automatically generated images

These people do not exist; a solution in relation to image rights © Josiane.Mothe@irit.fr

Applications for machine learning

- Images and interior design

UNIVERSITÉ DE JEAN JAURES <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1704.00090.pdf> © Josiane.Mothe@irit.fr

Applications for machine learning

- Images and agriculture

Chiu, M. T., Xu, X., Wei, Y., Huang, Z., Schwing, A. G., Brunner, R., ... & Shi, H. (2020). Agriculture-vision: A large aerial image database for agricultural pattern analysis. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, (pp. 2828-2838).

Applications for machine learning

Two main principles

- > Classification
 - Cancer / non cancer
 - Normal / abnormal
 - Weed / water / wheat / ...
- > Segmentation

<https://www6.inrae.fr/pfl-cepia/Axe-images/Tutoriel/La-segmentation-des-images>

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Applications for machine learning

Two main principles

- > Classification / Segmentation

Source <http://cs224d.stanford.edu/index.html>

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Applications – Generative or non generative AI?

Generative

Not all is generative AI

```

import sys
import os
import time
import random
import argparse
import cv2
import numpy as np
import tensorflow as tf
import tensorflow_hub as hub

def download_youtube_video(url, output_path):
    """Download a YouTube video to a local file"""
    yt = YouTube(url)
    video = yt.streams.get_highest_resolution()
    video.download(output_path)
    return video

def generate_image(prompt):
    """Generate an image from a text prompt using a generative model"""
    # Example prompt: "A landscape with a sunset over mountains"
    # The model would generate an image based on this prompt.

```


Aide à l'écriture d'articles de blogs, de presse, ...

Main principles

Non-supervised ML

- Data are not annotated, no apriori knowledge

Generalisation

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Main principles

Supervised ML

- From annotated examples

Task:
Learn to separate a **spanish mop** from a **Puli dog**.

From annotated examples
= Result is known for the examples

The model learns to categorise

And gets generalisation capabilities

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III. DATA REPRESENTATION

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Feature Engineering

Data representation

Engineered features

- Types of cap shape nominal values
- Annulus Boolean value (Y/N)
- Color of the Annulus
- Volva
- ...

<https://www.quora.com/danilo>

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Feature Engineering

Features will help in building a model (e.g. rules) to predict / decide whether it is edible

Couleur_du_chapeau	brun
Surface_du_chapeau	ecailleuse, mechuleuse, squameuse, veloutee
Type_de_marge	emousse
Dessous_du_chapeau	tubes
Couleur_sous_chapeau	blanc, gris, jaune, vert
Oxydation_du_chapeau	absence d oxydation
Insertion_chapeau_pied	echancres, emarginees
Couleur_du_pied	brun, gris
Pied_creux_ou_plein	pied plein
Forme_du_pied	claviforme, cylindrique, massue, t.fr

Label Edible

Feature Engineering

Features will help in building a model (e.g. rules) to predict / decide whether it is eatable

Couleur_du_chapeau	orange, rose, rouge
Surface_du_chapeau	brillante, ecailleuse, floconneuse, mechuleuse, squameuse, verrues
Type_de_marge	strie
Dessous_du_chapeau	lamelles
Couleur_sous_chapeau	blanc
Oxydation_du_chapeau	absence d oxydation
Insertion_chapeau_pied	libres
Espace_entre_lamelles	serrees
Type_de_lamelles	normal
Couleur_du_pied	blanc
Pied_creux_ou_plein	pied plein
Forme_du_pied	bulbeux, cylindrique, tubulaire, volve

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Label Poisonous

Data representation – depends on the data type

- Text – non structured
 - Indexing, term extraction
 - Vectors
- Images
 - Colors
 - NN
- Semi-structured data
 - Information extraction
- Structured data
 - Vectors: characteristics of each individuals
 - Matrices

Examples

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Types of variables / Features

- Quantitative Variable
 - Numerical feature
 - Arithmetic's can be applied with meaningful results.
- Examples
 - Continuous vs discrete
 - Discrete: variable with a finite number of values
 - Continuous: variable with an infinite number of values

Types of variables / Features

- Qualitative Variable
 - Non-umerical feature
 - Arithmetic's is not meaningful
- Examples
 - Dichotomous: nominal variables which have only two categories
 - Nominal: two or more categories with no order
 - Ordinal: two or more categories can be ordered or ranked

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Type of variables

- Number of failures of a system
 - Time needed to process a task
 - Color of eyes
 - Answer to the question: « do you think the system answers correctly »?
- Quantitative & discrete
 - Quantitative & continuous
 - Qualitative & nominal
 - Qualitative & ordinal

Variables

Supervised machine learning

Engineered features

Decision tree

Based on the feature values

And the label/annotation

Use in Machine learning

from Data to Models

Deep Learning – No engineered features

from Data to Models

QUIZ Questions

- What is the term used to describe the transformation of raw data into a format that is suitable for building machine learning models
- Answer:

QUIZ Questions

❑ In the context of deep learning, what is the purpose of an embedding layer when dealing with categorical data, such as words in text processing?

❑ Means:

Search

<https://www.baeldung.com/cs/neural-nets-embedding-layers>
<https://deepgram.com/ai-glossary/embedding-layer>

❑ Answer:

Machine learning approaches

Unsupervised

- ❑ Analysis of the data
 - Extract the model from the data
 - No train/test

Supervised Predictive

- ❑ Analysis of the training set
 - Extract the model from data
- ❑ Use the model on the test or data for which we need a prediction

III. UNSUPERVISED

Classification methods

- ❑ Agglomerative clustering
 - <https://online.stat.psu.edu/stat508/lesson/12/12.6>
- ❑ K-means

Agglomerative clustering (unsupervised)

```
given a dataset (d1, d2, d3, ...dN) of size N
# compute the distance matrix
for i=1 to N
  for j=1 to i
    dis_mat[i][j] = distance[di, dj]
each data point is a singleton cluster
repeat
  merge the two cluster having minimum distance
  update the distance matrix
until only a single cluster remains
```

<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/hierarchical-clustering/>

The idea is to aggregate the distances between the objects contained in the clusters.

- For clusters containing only one data point, the between-cluster distance is the between-object distance.
- For clusters containing multiple data points, the between-cluster distance is an agglomerative version of the between-object distances.

Agglomerative clustering (unsupervised)

- ❑ Distance between two objects

Name	Parametre	Fonction
Manhattan	1-distance	$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - y_i $
euclidienne	2-distance	$\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}$
Minkowski	p-distance	$\sqrt[p]{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - y_i ^p}$

Agglomerative clustering

Agglomerative distance

Agglomerative clustering

- Results in a hierarchy of partitions
- Dendrogram or tree that can be cut at different levels

Agglomerative clustering

- Ward criteria
 - minimum of the intra-cluster inertia or
 - maximum of the inter-group inertia

Inter-group inertia: mean of the squared distances from the center of gravity

K-means and variants

- Initialization:
 - Choose K group centroids
 - Cluster the objects (closest centroid)
 - First partition
 - Repeat
 - Calculate the new centroids considering the objects in the cluster
 - Recluster the objects
- Until either no changes, or a certain number of iterations, or ...

Classification centre mobiles

- Parameters - variants
 - Choice of the initial K centroids
 - Distance « closest »
 - New centroids

IV. SUPERVISED

Predictive analytics
Supervised : annotated data

A few supervised methods

- Simple/multiple linear regression
- Decision trees
- SVM
- NN and deep learning

Simple/Multiple linear regression

- Simple: Relationships between two continuous (quantitative) variables
 - One (simple) variable is regarded as the **predictor**/explanatory/independent variable
 - The other variable is regarded as the **response**/outcome/dependent variable
- Extract the trend / relationship that may exist between the predictor and the response
- Linear

Simple/Multiple linear regression

- fitted using the least squares (minimizes the sum of squared residuals) approach (or other)

Simple/Multiple linear regression

- More?
 - <https://online.stat.psu.edu/statprogram/stat501>
 - Simple linear regression
 - Multiple linear regression
 - Evaluation
 - <http://www.r-tutor.com/elementary-statistics>

Decision Tree

- The model predicts the value of a target (response) variable by learning simple decision rules inferred from the data features.
- Both categorical and continuous input/predictor and output/response variables

Illustration of Decision Tree

https://medium.com/@haydar_ailearning-data-science-day-12-decision-tree-fa83499f89fd

Decision Trees

- CART (Classification And Regression Tree)
 - Binary tree
 - A greedy approach is used to divide the space : **recursive binary splitting**.
 - All the values are lined up and different split points are tried and tested using a cost function. The split with the lowest cost is selected
 - Regression predictive modeling: the cost function is the sum squared error across all training samples

Decision Tree

- More?
- <http://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/tree.html>
- <https://machinelearningmastery.com/classification-and-regression-trees-for-machine-learning>
- <https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2016/04/complete-tutorial-tree-based-modeling-scratch-in-python/>

SVM

- Support Vector Machine
- Binary classification (multi-classes too)

www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~az/lectures/ml/lect2.pdf
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SVM

www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~az/lectures/ml/lect2.pdf
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SVM

- More?
- www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~az/lectures/ml/lect2.pdf (slides)
- cs229.stanford.edu/notes/cs229-notes3.pdf (textual)
- <https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/electrical-engineering-and-computer-science/6-034-artificial-intelligence-fall-2010/lecture-videos/lecture-16-learning-support-vector-machines/> (video)

Principles

Artificial Neural Network

https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mod%C3%A8les_du_neurone_biolgique

Perceptron (Rosenblatt, 1958)

<https://zestedesavoir.com/articles/1654/deep-learning-cest-quoi/>

Principles

Multilayer NN (1960 then 1980)

Principles

Principles

From NN to Deep Learning

- Convolutional NN
 - A convolutional layer applies filters
 - A filter produces a feature map
 - Reduces the size of the representation

Transformers

- Deep neural network architecture
- Comprises a set of encoding layers and a set of decoding layers.
- Each set comprises an embedding layer (e.g. word embedding).
- Finally, an output layer generates the final output.

Transformers - architecture

- An encoder consists of:
 - "Self-attention" layer
 - "Feed-forward" layer
- A decoder consists of:
 - "Self-attention" layer
 - "Feed-forward" layer
 - "Encoder-Decoder attention" layer

An attention "head" represents attention weights and. Multi-head attention is to run the attention mechanism multiple times in parallel and operates on the same input but extracts different features from this input.

Transformers

From NN to Deep Learning

Want to know more?

- Udacity (Google) <https://www.udacity.com/course/deep-learning--ud730>
- Coding <http://course.fast.ai>
- Tensorflow library: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>
- Keras: <https://elitedatascience.com/keras-tutorial-deep-learning-in-python>

QUIZ

What is the main difference between supervised and unsupervised learning in machine learning?

Answer:

QUIZ

Describe the role of the activation function in a neural network model. Why is it necessary?

Answer:

QUIZ

How the architecture and primary use cases of Transformers differ from those of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)?

Answer:

Evaluation measures

		Actual Value	
		Positive [have disease]	Negative [no disease]
Predicted Value	Positive [have disease]	TP	FP
	Negative [no disease]	FN	TN

$$\text{specificity} = \frac{TN}{FP + TN} \quad \text{fall-out} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

$$\text{recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad \text{precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Evaluation measures

ROC

Plots the true positive rate (sensitivity) against the false positive rate (1 - specificity) at various threshold settings

The area under the ROC curve (AUC)
A model whose predictions are 100% wrong has an AUC of 0.0, while one whose predictions are 100% correct has an AUC of 1.0.

Loss function (objective / cost function)

- Quantifies the difference between the predicted outputs and the true outputs
- Measures of error that the model needs to minimize

Examples of Loss functions:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h7BpEHGVNc>

Evaluation in supervised methods

- Train / Test Split
 - A training set (to calculate the model)
 - A testing set (to check the results)
 - [A validation set]
- How to choose the training/testing sets?
 - 80 / 20

Evaluation in supervised methods

- 10-folds cross validation

Data quality

- Completeness of the training data set
 - Lack of examples

Over-fitting

Data quality

- Completeness of the features
 - Lack of values in training or testing

Ind	Weight	Height	Hair	Class
I1		1.12	Blond	Child
I2	75	1.80	Brown	Adult
I3	80	1.74		Adult
I4	18		Brown	Child

Ind	Weight	Height	Hair	Class
I8		1.30	Blond	?

QUIZ

- What is the purpose of using a confusion matrix in classification tasks, and what information does it provide?
- Answer:

QUIZ

Explain the difference between cross-validation and a train-test split in the context of model evaluation

Answer:

[Redacted answer text]

[Redacted answer text]

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Artificial Intelligence for Earth Observation Data Analysis

- ✓ Introduction to Deep Learning for EO
- ✓ Read and visualize satellite images

Earth observation images from satellites are available in different formats and with different number of channels. Because of this special libraries are often required to read, process and visualize them. In this lab we will be using TorchGeo, which is a PyTorch domain library made of popular datasets, model architectures, and common image transformations for geospatial data. It support models pre-trained on different multispectral sensors. [Read more about TorchGeo from its creators.](#)

First we install the libraries that are not already available in colab, in this case we only need to install torchgeo. This might take some time.

```
%%capture  
!pip install torchgeo
```

We then import the libraries that we will be using.

```
import torch  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
import os  
from torchgeo.datasets import EuroSAT100  
import random
```

From torchgeo we will download the EuroSAT100 which is a subset of 100 images from the EuroSAT dataset. Find out more about the EuroSAT dataset [here](#) and [here](#).

```
# download EuroSAT100 images in a local directory  
dataset = EuroSAT100(root=".", download=True)
```

EuroSAT iamdes are from Sentinel 2 and are provided with [13 spectral bands](#). Each element

of the dataset is a dictionary containing the image and its label.

```
# what is the shape of the first image? How many bands?
print(f"Shape of the first image: {dataset[0]['image'].shape}")
```

We can view the name of each class in the dataset with its corresponding label value.

```
TIFF_DATA_BASE_PATH = "/content/ds/images/remote_sensing/otherDatasets/sentinel_2/tif"
classes = sorted(os.listdir(TIFF_DATA_BASE_PATH))
classes_dict = dict(enumerate(classes))
print(f"Class names: {classes_dict}")
```

We can visualize a sample of images from the dataset, we pick the images randomly. For this, we will use the Blue, Green and Red bands only.

```
# plot 5 randomly picked images
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(16, 4))
random_indices = random.sample(range(len(dataset)), 5) # Select 5 random indices

for i, idx in enumerate(random_indices):
    sample = dataset[idx]
    image_rgb = torch.stack([sample['image'][j, :, :] for j in [3, 2, 1]], dim=0) # S
    label = sample['label']
    image_rgb = image_rgb.permute(1, 2, 0)
    normalized_image = (image_rgb - torch.min(image_rgb)) / (torch.max(image_rgb) - to
    ax = fig.add_subplot(1, 5, i + 1, xticks=[], yticks=[])
    plt.imshow(normalized_image)
    ax.set_title(classes_dict[label.item()])
    ax.axis('off')

plt.show()
```

✓ Classify Earth observation images with deep learning models

Deep learning models are the state of the art in image classification. In this practical we will learn how to build a simple deep learning image classification model with pytorch and use it to classify satellite images. We will then use the state of the art model architectures available in the torchvision package to perform the same task.

✓ Pytorch and tensors

Pytorch is a framework that allows you to work with tensors, build and train neural networks. Pytorch also provides a very simple way to move your data and networks to GPUs

PyTorch also provides a very simple way to move your data and networks to GPU.

With PyTorch we are going to be working with tensors. A tensor is a generalization of vectors and matrices and can have 1 or more dimensions.

A GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) is a specialized processor that speeds up computation when training neural networks compared to a CPU (Central Processing Unit). If we have a GPU we want to make sure that we use it. We check if we have GPU, if not, we will run our models on CPU and set the device accordingly.

```
# Check if GPU is available and set device accordingly
if torch.cuda.is_available():
    device = torch.device('cuda')
else:
    device = torch.device('cpu')

# print the device you are using
print("Using device:", device)
```

✓ 1 - Define the dataset

To train our CNN, we will use part of the data, and we will leave another part out to use for testing the CNN. We will also use a part of the training data to validate the training. Torchgeo has already split the data into 60% for training, 20% for validation and 20% for testing.

We create dataset objects for our train, validation and test sets from the dataset that we downloaded selecting the spectral bands we want to use.

Note: We are using Sentinel-2 data, be mindful of the spatial resolution of the chosen bands. See [this link](#) for spatial resolutions of Sentinel-2 spectral bands.

```
# using the 3 R G B bans, to use the NIR band add B08
train_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='train', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'))
valid_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='val', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'))
test_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='test', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'))
```

We define a function to plot the number of samples in each class.

```
def plot_from_dict(dict_obj, plot_title, ax, color):
    return( ax.bar(range(len(dict_obj)), list(dict_obj.values()), align='center', color=color)
            ax.set_title(plot_title), ax.set_xlabel('classes'), ax.set_ylabel('samples')
            ax.set_xticklabels(dict_obj.keys(), rotation =45))
```

After creating the data set splits. we can look at the proportion of each class in in each split.

We want to see whether our datasets are balanced or imbalanced in favor of one or another class.

We define a function that counts the number of samples in each class and another one to draw the plot of the values for each data split.

```
# Function to count the number of samples in each class for each dataset
def get_class_count(dataset):
    count_dict = {}
    for class_id in classes_dict:
        count = 0
        for sample in dataset:
            value = sample['label'].item()
            if value == class_id:
                count += 1
            count_dict[value] = count
    return(count_dict)

print(f"Number of samples in each split \n train: {len(train_dataset)}, valid: {len(va
```

We plot the number of samples in each class for each train/valid/test set

```
fig, axes = plt.subplots(nrows=1, ncols=3, figsize=(16,4))

my_colors = ['pink', 'blue', 'purple']

plot_from_dict(get_class_count(train_dataset), plot_title="Train Set", ax=axes[0], col
plot_from_dict(get_class_count(valid_dataset), plot_title="Valid Set", ax=axes[1], col
plot_from_dict(get_class_count(test_dataset), plot_title="Test Set", ax=axes[2], color

plt.show()
```

✓ 2- Load the data

We use Pytorch's data loader to read the data and put it in memory in batches.

```
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader
from torchgeo.datasets import stack_samples

BATCH_SIZE = 10
train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True, coll
valid_loader = DataLoader(valid_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True, coll
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True, collat
```

✓ 3- Define the model

✓ Convolutional Neural Networks

We will use pytorch to build a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to classify images from the EuroSAT dataset. The CNN that we will use requires that we specify the number of channels of the input images. All our images must have the same number of channels.

We get the number of channels from the first image in our list of images for the train set.

```
# n channel images
nb_channels = train_dataset[0]['image'].shape[0]
print(f"Number of input channels: {nb_channels}")
```

We will now define our CNN, subclassing the `torch.nn.Module`, which is the base class for all neural network modules. We build a network with 3 convolutional layers and two fully connected layers. We will also add pooling layers, ReLU activation, flattening and dropout.

```
from torch import nn

class CNN(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self):
        super(CNN, self).__init__()
        # convolutional layer (sees 3x64x64 image tensor)
        self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(nb_channels, 32, 7, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 32x60x60 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 32x30x30 tensor)
        self.conv2 = nn.Conv2d(32, 32, 7, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 32x26x26 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 32x13x13 tensor)
        self.conv3 = nn.Conv2d(32, 64, 7, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 64x9x9 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 64x4x4 tensor)
        # max pooling layer
        self.pool = nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2)
        self.flat = nn.Flatten()
        # linear layer (64 * 4 * 4 -> 500)
        self.fc1 = nn.Linear(64 * 4 * 4, 500)
        # linear layer (500 -> 10)
```

```

self.fc2 = nn.Linear(500, 10) # to 10 classes
# dropout layer (p=0.25)
self.dropout = nn.Dropout(0.25)

def forward(self, x):
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv1(x)))
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv2(x)))
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv3(x)))
    x = self.flat(x)
    x = self.dropout(x)
    x = F.relu(self.fc1(x))
    x = self.dropout(x)
    x = self.fc2(x)
    return x

```

The main building block of a CNN is the convolutional kernel or filter. When convolutional kernels/filters are applied to an input, the output is a filtered image also referred to as a feature map. In our CNN we apply 32 7x7 kernels to our input, in the first convolutional layer.

We apply ReLU activation to the output of the convolutional layers, which changes all the negative values to 0.

Pooling layers reduce the size of the input. The illustration below shows the application of a 2x2 maxpooling filter/kernel to a 4x4 patch with stride 2. The size of the patch is reduced in half.

Max pooling with 2x2 filter and stride = 2

Image by [Aphex34](#), [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

The flatten operation transforms the tensor by flattening it, effectively removing all but one of its dimensions. Our multi-dimension tensor is effectively transformed into a single dimension tensor.

Dropout is applied in order to prevent overfitting when training the network. It causes the outputs of a layer to be randomly set to 0 at the defined rate of 0.25 in our CNN.

Linear layers apply a linear transformation to the input. They are fully connected layers for which we need to specify the size of the input. We can calculate the output for our convolutional layers with the following formula $(W-F+2P)/S + 1$ ([source](#)). Where W is the input size, F is the size of the neurons in the convolutional layer, S is the stride and P is the amount of zero padding used on the border. In our CNN, for the first convolutional layer we have $W = 64$, $F = 7$, $S = 1$ (default) and $P = 1$.

Linear or fully connected layer.

We now instantiate our previously defined CNN class to construct our classification model.

```
classification_model = CNN()
```

We can print the model to view all its components with all their parameters and their values.

```
print(classification_model)
```

✓ 4- Train the model

We load the model to the device, this is useful if we have GPU, because so far, everything we have done was done on CPU. If we are only using a CPU the model simply stays on the CPU otherwise it will be loaded onto the GPU.

```
# load model on device
classification_model = classification_model.to(device)
```

Before we start training our CNN we need to define several hyperparameters that determine how the CNN will train.

The number of epochs defines how many times the entire dataset goes through the network. The learning rate determine how the network converges to a small error value, it has a small positive value, and defines the step size that the model will take at each epoch as it moves towards a small loss.

```
# define number of epochs and learning rate
num_epochs = 20
learning_rate = 0.001
```

We choose a criterion or loss function based on our problem. As we are performing multi-class image classification, `nn.CrossEntropyLoss` is suitable ([read the corresponding Pytorch doc](#)).

```
# define loss function
criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()
```

We choose an optimization algorithm, it reduces the loss as the network trains by updating its parameters. We are using the Adam optimizer ([read about it here](#)).

```
# define optimizer
optimizer = torch.optim.Adam(classification_model.parameters(), lr = learning_rate)
```

We define a function to train our model and save the trained model to a specific path.

```
# function to train model and save trained model

def train_model(current_model, save_path):

    # minimum bound for the validation loss
    valid_loss_min = np.Inf

    # dictionary to keep track of train and validation losses
    loss_stats = { 'train': [], 'valid': [] }

    print('Training for {} epochs'.format(num_epochs))

    for epoch in range(1, num_epochs+1):

        # keep track of training and validation loss
        train_loss = 0.0
        valid_loss = 0.0

        # Put model in train mode
        current_model.train()

        # train the model
        # loop over the data loader
        for sample in train_loader:
            # move tensors to the previously selected device
            data = sample['image']
            target = sample['label']
            data, target = data.to(device), target.to(device)

            # reset the gradients of all optimized variables (learnable weight parameter)
            optimizer.zero_grad()

            # perform forward pass, get the model predictions for the batch
            output = current_model(data)
            # calculate the batch loss
            loss = criterion(output, target)
            # perform backward pass, compute gradients of the loss with respect to all
            loss.backward()
            # perform an optimization step (parameter update)
            optimizer.step()

        # update the training loss
        train_loss += loss.item()*data.size(0)
```

```

train_loss += loss.item() * data.size(0)

# put the model in eval mode (dropout is deactivated)
current_model.eval()
# validate the model on the validation data set
for sample in valid_loader:
    data = sample['image']
    target = sample['label']
    # move tensors to the previously selected device
    data, target = data.to(device), target.to(device)

    # perform forward pass, get the model predictions for the batch
    output = current_model(data)
    # calculate the batch loss
    loss = criterion(output, target)

    # update validation loss
    valid_loss += loss.item()*data.size(0)

# calculate average losses
train_loss = train_loss/len(train_loader.sampler)
valid_loss = valid_loss/len(valid_loader.sampler)

# save loss stats for the epoch into the loss dictionary
loss_stats['train'].append(train_loss)
loss_stats['valid'].append(valid_loss)

# print the epoch's training/validation statistics
print('Epoch: {} \tTraining Loss: {:.6f} \tValidation Loss: {:.6f}'.format(
    epoch, train_loss, valid_loss))

# save the model if validation loss has decreased from previously lowest loss
if valid_loss <= valid_loss_min:
    torch.save(current_model.state_dict(), save_path)
    valid_loss_min = valid_loss

# plot train and validation losses
train_val_loss_df = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(loss_stats).reset_index().melt(id_vars=
fig, axes = plt.subplots(nrows=1, ncols=1, figsize=(20,6))
axes.set(xticks=train_val_loss_df.epochs.values)
sns.lineplot(data=train_val_loss_df, x = "epochs", y="value", hue="variable").set_

```

We define the path where we want to save the trained model.

```

# path to save new model
save_path = 'simple_CNN.pt'

```

We train the model by calling our train_model function and passing it the model and the previously defined path.

```

import time
import numpy as np
import torch.nn.functional as F
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns

# list to keep track of train time
train_time = []

# train the model and save the best model to the save path
t_start = time.time()

train_model(classification_model,save_path)

t_final = time.time()
train_time.append(t_final - t_start)

```

✓ 5- Make a prediction

During training we saved the model with the lowest validation loss. We will load this saved model to test it by making predictions on the test data.

```
classification_model.load_state_dict(torch.load(save_path))
```

We define a function to test our best model on the test data set.

```

#number of classes
NB_CLS = len(classes)

# list to keep track of test accuracy
test_accuracy_overall = []

def test_model(current_model):

    # keep track of the test loss
    test_loss = 0.0

    # keep track of correct and incorrect classifications for each class
    class_correct = list(0. for i in range(NB_CLS))
    class_total = list(0. for i in range(NB_CLS))

    # put the model in eval mode
    # all layers know the model is in eval mode
    # dropout is deactivated
    current_model.eval()

    # deactivate the autograd engine for reduced memory usage
    # no backpropagation is performed, gradients are not calculated
    with torch.no_grad():

```

```

# iterate over test data
for sample in test_loader:

    data = sample['image']
    target = sample['label']

    # move tensors to the previously selected device
    data, target = data.to(device), target.to(device)

    # perform forward pass, compute predicted outputs by passing inputs to the
    output = current_model(data)
    # calculate the batch loss
    loss = criterion(output, target)
    # update test loss
    test_loss += loss.item()*data.size(0)

    # convert output probabilities to predicted class
    _, pred = torch.max(output, 1)

    # compare predictions to true label
    correct_tensor = pred.eq(target.data.view_as(pred))

    # Check which device is used to move tensor to cpu if needed
    # convert tensor to numpy
    if device == 'cpu':
        correct = np.squeeze(correct_tensor.numpy())
    else:
        correct = np.squeeze(correct_tensor.cpu().numpy())

    # calculate the test accuracy for each class
    for i in range(len(target.data)):
        label = target.data[i]
        class_correct[label] += correct[i].item()
        class_total[label] += 1

# average test loss
test_loss = test_loss/len(test_loader.sampler)
print('Test Loss: {:.6f}\n'.format(test_loss))

# for each class print the statistics
for i in range(NB_CLS):
    if class_total[i] > 0:
        print('Test Accuracy of %5s: %2d%% (%2d/%2d)' % (
            classes[i], 100 * class_correct[i] / class_total[i],
            np.sum(class_correct[i]), np.sum(class_total[i])))
    else:
        print('Test Accuracy of {}: N/A (no training examples)'.format(classes[i]))

test_accuracy_overall.append(100 * np.sum(class_correct) / np.sum(class_total))

print('\nTest Accuracy (Overall): %2d%% (%2d/%2d)' % (
    100. * np.sum(class_correct) / np.sum(class_total),

```

```

np.sum(class_correct), np.sum(class_total)))

# test model to see how well it performs on unseen data
test_model(classification_model)

```

✓ 6- Visualize sample results

We can visualize images from one test batch with their actual label and their predicted label.

```

# obtain one batch of test images
dataiter = iter(test_loader)
samples = next(dataiter)
images, labels = samples['image'], samples['label']
images.numpy()

# move tensors to the previously selected device
images = images.to(device)

# get sample outputs
output = classification_model(images)

# convert output probabilities to predicted class
_, preds_tensor = torch.max(output, 1)

if device == 'cpu':
    preds = np.squeeze(preds_tensor.numpy())
else:
    preds = np.squeeze(preds_tensor.cpu().numpy())

fig = plt.figure(figsize=(20, 6))
nb_images = 10

def normalize_image(image):
    return (image - torch.min(image)) / (torch.max(image) - torch.min(image))

for j in np.arange(nb_images):
    ax = fig.add_subplot(2, 5, j+1, xticks=[], yticks=[])
    plt.imshow(np.transpose(normalize_image(images.cpu()[j]), (2, 1, 0))[:, :, :3])
    ax.set_title("{} [{}]" .format(classes[preds[j]], classes[labels[j]]),
                color=("blue" if preds[j]==labels[j].item() else "magenta"))

# delete model to free memory
del classification_model

```

✓ 7 - Test the effect of different values of hyperparameters

Each hyperparameter has an effect on the performance of the model. We can try to improve the model's performance by changing the value of each parameter, one at a time and then looking at the model's performance to see how it is affected.

```
classification_model2 = CNN()
classification_model2 = classification_model2.to(device)

# Try different learning rate
learning_rate = 0.0001

# Try different number of epochs
num_epochs = 50

# Try different loss function
criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()

# Try different optimizer
optimizer = torch.optim.AdamW(classification_model2.parameters(), lr=learning_rate)

# Try different batch sizes
BATCH_SIZE = 5
train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True)
valid_loader = DataLoader(valid_dataset, batch_size = 10, shuffle = True)
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size = 20, shuffle = True)

# path to save new model
save_path = 'simple_CNN2.pt'

t_start = time.time()

train_model(classification_model2, save_path)

t_final = time.time()

train_time.append(t_final - t_start)

classification_model2.load_state_dict(torch.load(save_path))

test_model(classification_model2)

del classification_model2
```

✓ 8- Normalize and augment images

We normalize the images using the mean and standard deviation of the pixel values of the dataset.

```
means = torch.tensor([1087.1959, 1000.6182, 893.7279])
stds = torch.tensor([313.6509, 361.3129, 529.4100])
```

We create a function to transform the pixel values into their normalized values.

```
class MeanStdNormalize(K.IntensityAugmentationBase2D):
    """Normalize channels using mean/std values."""

    def __init__(self, means: Tensor, stds: Tensor) -> None:
        super().__init__(p=1)
        self.flags = {'means': means.view(1, -1, 1, 1), 'stds': stds.view(1, -1, 1, 1)}

    def apply_transform(
        self,
        input: Tensor,
        params: dict[str, Tensor],
        flags: dict[str, int],
        transform: Tensor | None = None,
    ) -> Tensor:
        #return (input - flags['means']) / (flags['stds'])

        normalized_input = (input - flags['means']) / flags['stds']
        normalized_input = normalized_input.squeeze()
        return normalized_input
```

```
transforms = AugmentationSequential(MeanStdNormalize(means, stds), data_keys=['image'])
```

We recreate the datasets with the normalized values using the transforms we just defined.

```
train_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='train', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'), transform=transforms)
valid_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='val', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'), transform=transforms)
test_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='test', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'), transform=transforms)
```

```
BATCH_SIZE = 5
train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True)
valid_loader = DataLoader(valid_dataset, batch_size = 10, shuffle = True)
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size = 20, shuffle = True)
```

```
classification_model3 = CNN()
classification_model3 = classification_model3.to(device)
```

```
save_path = 'simple_CNN3.pt'
```

```
num_epochs = 30
optimizer = torch.optim.AdamW(classification_model3.parameters(), lr=learning_rate)
```

```
t_start = time.time()
```

```
train_model(classification_model3, save_path)
```

```

....._.....\....._....., ....._.....,
t_final = time.time()

train_time.append(t_final - t_start)

classification_model3.load_state_dict(torch.load(save_path))

test_model(classification_model3)

del classification_model3

```

In addition to normalizing the data we can also augment it by applying random flips, rotation and other transforms. This is useful in cases where we do not have a lot of data to train.

```

# image augmentation, random flip and rotation in addition to normalization
# you can also add indices

transforms = AugmentationSequential(
    K.RandomHorizontalFlip(p=0.5),
    K.RandomVerticalFlip(p=0.5),
    K.RandomAffine(degrees=(0, 90), p=0.25),
    K.RandomGaussianBlur(kernel_size=(3, 3), sigma=(0.1, 2.0), p=0.25),
    K.RandomResizedCrop(size=(64, 64), scale=(0.8, 1.0), p=0.25),
    MeanStdNormalize(means, stds),
    data_keys=['image'],
)

train_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='train', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'), trans
valid_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='val', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'), transfo
test_dataset = EuroSAT100(root='.', split='test', bands=('B02', 'B03', 'B04'), transfo

train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True)
valid_loader = DataLoader(valid_dataset, batch_size = 10, shuffle = True)
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size = 20, shuffle = True)

classification_model4 = CNN()
classification_model4 = classification_model4.to(device)

save_path = 'simple_CNN4.pt'

num_epochs = 30
optimizer = torch.optim.AdamW(classification_model4.parameters(), lr=learning_rate)

t_start = time.time()

train_model(classification_model4, save_path)

t_final = time.time()

```

```

train_time.append(t_final - t_start)

classification_model4.load_state_dict(torch.load(save_path))

test_model(classification_model4)

del classification_model4

```

✓ 9- Updating the model number of layers, filter size

We have changed hyperparameter values, normalized and augmented data, to improve the model's performance. Now we will update the model itself to try to improve our results.

Our initial CNN had three conv layers with 7x7 kernels. We will replace them with 3x3 kernels and add a fourth conv layer.

```

# initial CNN
# print(CNN())

# deeper model with more conv layers
# 4 conv layers instead of 3
# smaller kernels 3x3 instead of 7x7
class CNN2(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self):
        super(CNN2, self).__init__()
        # convolutional layer (sees 3x64x64 image tensor)
        self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(nb_channels, 32, 3, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 32x64x64 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 32x32x32 tensor)
        self.conv2 = nn.Conv2d(32, 32, 3, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 32x32x32 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 32x16x16 tensor)
        self.conv3 = nn.Conv2d(32, 64, 3, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 64x16x16 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 64x8x8 tensor)
        self.conv4 = nn.Conv2d(64, 64, 3, padding=1)
        # convolutional layer (out 64x8x8 tensor)
        # pool below layer (out 64x4x4 tensor)
        # max pooling layer
        self.pool = nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2)
        # linear layer (64 * 4 * 4 -> 500)
        self.fc1 = nn.Linear(64 * 4 * 4, 500)
        # linear layer (500 -> 10)
        self.fc2 = nn.Linear(500, 10)
        # dropout layer (p=0.25)
        self.dropout = nn.Dropout(0.25)

```

```

def forward(self, x):

```

```

def forward(self, x):
    # pass through each conv followed by pool layers
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv1(x)))
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv2(x)))
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv3(x)))
    x = self.pool(F.relu(self.conv4(x)))
    # flatten the output of the last conv-pool
    x = x.view(-1, 64 * 4 * 4)
    # dropout added to prevent overfitting
    x = self.dropout(x)
    x = F.relu(self.fc1(x))
    x = self.dropout(x)
    x = self.fc2(x)
    return x

classification_model5 = CNN2()
classification_model5 = classification_model5.to(device)

# Try different learning rate
learning_rate = 0.0001

# Try different number of epochs
num_epochs = 30

# Try different loss function
criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()

# Try different optimizer
optimizer = torch.optim.AdamW(classification_model5.parameters(), lr=learning_rate)

# Try different batch size
BATCH_SIZE = 5
train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size = BATCH_SIZE, shuffle = True)
valid_loader = DataLoader(valid_dataset, batch_size = 10, shuffle = True)
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size = 20, shuffle = True)

# path to save new model
save_path = 'simple_CNN5.pt'

t_start = time.time()

train_model(classification_model5, save_path)

t_final = time.time()

train_time.append(t_final - t_start)

classification_model5.load_state_dict(torch.load(save_path))

test_model(classification_model5)

del classification_model5

```

✓ 10- Use a state of the art model from torchivision

There are neural network architectures that have been shown to perform extremely well on common image classification tasks. One such model is the ResNet. (Read about it [here](#).)

Instead of trying to build our own best classifier from scratch we can try and reuse ResNet and see how well it performs on our data.

Introduction to EO data

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AI4AGRI Summer School 2024, Brasov, Romania
 9th May 2024

First remote sensing system ?

Remote sensing broadens our capabilities in sensing, so that we can collect remote information not only in the visible part of the em spectrum, but also, for example, in the microwaves of infrared

The more the wavelength and the object dimension are comparable, the higher is the intensity of the interaction

<http://remote-sensing.net/concepts.html>

BANDS INTERVALS

VIEW ANGLE

TIME

POLARIZATION

ACTIVE AND PASSIVE SYSTEMS

ADVANTAGES OF MICROWAVES

SCATTERING MECHANISMS (1)

Surface scattering is the dominant mechanism for rough surfaces and it is characterized by single reflections. Note that this scattering type can only be considered in situations where the rms height of the surface is much lower than the wavelength of the illuminating wave. It also adequately explains the low return observed for most of the water bodies imaged by a SAR instrument root mean square

SCATTERING MECHANISMS (3)

In **volume scattering** before the wave backpropagates to the receiver, an interaction between the wave and the medium occurs through multiple reflections. Note that backscattered power is attenuated during this process

SCATTERING MECHANISMS (2)

A **double bounce mechanism** is where the wave is scattered by two plane faces. The wave undergoes a reflection from each surface and will return in the direction from whence it came. When city streets or buildings are lined up in such a way that the incoming radar pulses are able to bounce off the streets and then bounce again off the buildings (called a double-bounce) and directly back towards the radar they appear very bright (white) in radar images. Roads and highways are flat surfaces and so appear dark

Therefore...
➔

SCATTERING MECHANISMS and BACKSCATTERING

Optical image

Radar image

EO data are particularly suitable for vegetation monitoring

ATMOSPHERIC TRANSMISSIVITY

Spatial resolution:

minimum distance between two points allowing the sensor to distinguish them

Spectral resolution:

minimum wavelength (frequency) distance at which measures can be assumed independent each other

Radiometric resolution:

Minimum difference between the values of the measured parameter that the sensor can detect

COPERNICUS SENTINEL PROGRAM: A long-term operational perspective

SATELLITES.. MORE SATELLITES.. (DATA.. MORE DATA)

CUBESAT CONSTELLATIONS

The screenshot shows the Planet website interface. The main heading is 'Real-Time Satellite Monitoring with Planet'. Below it, a text block states: 'With roughly 200 Dove satellites in orbit, PlanetScope Monitoring provides a high-resolution, continuous, and complete view of the world from above, every day.' A prominent 'GET STARTED' button is visible at the bottom left of the main content area.

DATA PROCESSING FROM EARTH TO SPACE

The amount of available data is increasing at a very fast pace

New efficient processing procedures are required

Reduce the time to receive the information and limit bandwidth usage

Flexible, robust, and requiring low computation burden AI models

Applications of SAR in agriculture

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AI4AGRI Summer School 2024, Brasov, Romania
9th May 2024

SCATTERING AND ROUGHNESS IN SOILS

Smooth ($\sigma^\circ \sim 0$)

Moderately rough (σ° is low)

Very rough (σ° increases)

THE FORWARD PROBLEM

Good estimation of the surface soil moisture obtained by exploiting the EO-data retrieved by Sentinel-1 SAR product

Poggio Renatico 04/23/2018

What are the scatterers in the volume scattering?

Courtesy, T. Le Toan, CESBIO

The best correlation between σ° and biomass is obtained at a frequency which depends on dimensions of vegetation elements

Crop Discrimination through Time Evolution of Backscattering

F. Del Frate et al., "Crop classification using Multiconfiguration C-Band SAR data," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 41, n. 7, 2003

RICE FIELDS MONITORING

JERS-1 SAR measurements, L band, HH pol., $\theta=38.5^\circ$
 Site: Kedah-Perlis paddy plain (Malaysia)
 σ° vs. day after planting, average field values (by Rosenqvist, 1999)

Low σ° 's over flat flooded soil, before growth.

Increase mainly due to soil-stem double bounce

The basic concept of the retrieval procedure is to assume that the fields of the same crop type have a similar growth cycle

Network input: multitemporal σ° 's
 Network output: parameters characterizing the vegetation cycle in time.
 Network topology: 48-35-20-3

ASAR WSM 150m spatial resolution (75m pixel spacing), acquired 15th July 2007, descending pass, polarisation HH.

ASAR WSM 150m spatial resolution (75m pixel spacing), acquired 12th August 2006, descending pass, polarisation HH.

Inundated areas are clearly visible in this Envisat ASAR image acquired during floods in China in July 2007.

POST FIRE VEGETATION REGROWTH MONITORING

DATA FUSION SCHEME

OPTICAL VHR

SAR VHR

Vigor map

Heterogeneity map

GLCM TEXTURE INFORMATION (1)

Improve the definition of context by means of more rigorous textural features

➔ Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM, Haralick et al., 1973)

0	0	1	1
0	0	1	1
0	2	2	2
2	2	3	3

The matrix is computed with reference to a predefined box in the image, to a predefined number of gray levels, pixel distance (d) and direction (q)

The element P_{ij} of the matrix says how many times the element with gray level i is distant d pixels, in q direction, from an element with gray level j

4 gray levels (0, 1, 2, 3)
d=1 and q=0°

$$P(1,0^\circ) = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 2 & 4 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 6 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

GLCM TEXTURE INFORMATION (2)

GLCM parameters

- Shift
- Direction
- Quantization levels
- Window size

**SEARCH FOR OPTIMUM
VALUE/MEASURE**

GLCM measures

1. Mean $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} i p_{ij}$
2. Variance $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} p_{ij} (i - \mu)^2$
3. Homogeneity $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} \frac{p_{ij}}{(i-j)^2}$
4. Contrast $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} p_{ij} (i-j)^2$
5. Dissimilarity $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} p_{ij} |i-j|$
6. Entropy $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} p_{ij} (-\ln p_{ij})$
7. Energy $\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} (p_{ij})^2$
8. Correlation $\frac{\sum_{i,j=0}^{N-1} (i - \mu_i)(j - \mu_j) p_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sigma_i^2 \sigma_j^2}}$

Applications of SAR data in agriculture

Giorgia Guerrisi, Tor Vergata University of Rome, giorgia.guerrisi@uniroma2.it
AI4AGRI Summer School 2024, Brasov, Romania
9th May 2024

SAR data in agriculture

Applications:

- **Crop identification and crop planting area mapping:** use of different polarization/frequency combinations, use of multitemporal data.
- **Crop and cropland parameter extraction:** estimation of crop height, Leaf Area Index, biomass, Estimation of surface roughness, soil moisture,
- **Crop yield estimation.**

SAR data in agriculture

- Spatial information;
- All-weather conditions;
- High sensitivity to geometrical and dielectric properties of the target.

Optical vs. SAR data in agriculture

- Optical remote sensing methods for monitoring and studying crop growth status and yield are generally characterized by a **combination of different bands/features** used to build **relationships with the crop bio-physical eco-physiological parameters**, such as leaf area index (LAI), biomass, chlorophyll content, plant water content.
- Optical images are **easily interpreted** (crop planting area estimation, growth monitoring, yield prediction...).
- Optical data are affected by **weather conditions**.

Advantages of SAR data

- SAR is an **active remote sensing** method: it allows to collect data despite of light and weather conditions.
- SAR remote sensing is **sensitive to the dielectric and geometrical characteristics** of the plants.
- SAR has a **penetrating property**, and depending on the frequency, it can obtain information below the vegetation canopy cover.
- SAR remote sensing can use **different imaging parameters** to obtain information, such as the incident angles and the polarization configurations of the sensor.

SAR satellite missions

Mission (Organization)	Spatial/Temporal resolution	Launch Date	Data availability
Sentinel-1 (ESA)	5 m / 6 days	03/04/2014	Public
COSMO-SkyMed (ASI)	(az. x ra.) 0.3 x 0.5-40 x 6 m / 16 days	18/12/2019	Commercial
ALOS-2 (JAXA)	1-1000 m / 14 days	24/05/2014	Commercial

Copernicus and Sentinel missions

- Copernicus is a European program that provide free satellite and in-situ information.
- Sentinel missions are ESA missions based on a constellation of satellites developed within the Copernicus program which provide robust datasets for Copernicus services.

Sentinel-1 mission

- Two identical radar imagery satellites in the same orbit.
- Dual polarisation and very short revisit times.
- C-band, operating in four exclusive imaging modes.
- Different resolution (down to 5 m) and coverage (up to 400 km).
- Ice, oil spills, and ships monitoring, marine winds and waves, agriculture, deforestation, land deformation, emergency.

Sentinel-1 data

- Acquisition modes: Stripmap (SM), Interferometric Wide Swath (IW), Extra Wide Swath (EW), Wave (WV).
- Processing levels: Level-0 Raw, Level-1 SLC (Single Look Complex), Level-1 GRD (Ground Range Detected), Level-2 OCN (Ocean).
- Single polarisation (VV or HH) for WV mode and dual polarisation (VV+VH or HH+HV) or single polarisation (HH or VV) for SM, IW and EW modes.

Sentinel-1 data

- The IW swath mode is the main acquisition mode over land and satisfies the majority of service requirements.
- Level-1 data are the generally available products intended for most data users.

Sentinel-1 data

- IW Level-1 products

Sentinel-1 data

- Spatial resolutions depend on the acquisition mode and the level of processing.

Mode	Incidence Angle	Resolution	Swath Width	Polarization (H = Horizontal V = Vertical)
Stripmap	20 - 45	5 x 5 m	80 km	HH+HV, VH+VV, HH, VV
Interferometric Wide swath	29 - 46	5 x 20 m	250 km	HH+HV, VH+VV, HH, VV
Extra Wide swath	19 - 47	20 x 40 m	400 km	HH+HV, VH+VV, HH, VV
Wave	22 - 35 35 - 38	5 x 5 m	20 x 20 km	HH, VV

Soil moisture

- Soil moisture is the **water stored in the upper soil layer**.
- It is a crucial variable in a wide variety of applications (e.g., numerical weather prediction, flood forecasting, agricultural drought assessment, water resources management, greenhouse gas accounting, ...).

Soil moisture

- Soil moisture sensors provide **punctual measurements**, but a spatialized information is needed.

Soil moisture in agriculture

- Agriculture applications: plant water stress, soil moisture maps, smart irrigation, drought monitoring

SAR satellite missions for Soil Moisture

Mission (Organization)	Spatial/Temporal resolution	Launch Date	Data availability
SMAP (Soil Moisture Active/Passive) (NASA)	36 km / 6 hours - 3 days	31/01/2015	Public
SMOS (Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity) (ESA)	30 x 50 km / 3 days	02/11/2009	Public

Requirement for the exercise

- S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20240428T042950_20240428T043015_053629_06831B_163D.SAFE.zip input file
- Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem Account
- brasov_ndvi_aoi.kml file
- ESA SNAP Toolboxes
- ISMN account
- Google Colab notebooks
- GEE code link (<https://code.earthengine.google.com/ccd477cf5a5e7b283df6bd5506a35aad>)

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Explore data → Copernicus Browser

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Create an area of interest → Upload a file to create an area of interest

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Create an area of interest → Upload a file to create an area of interest

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Search → Sentinel-1 Level-1 GRD

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Search → Time range

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Product info → Download

ESA SNAP

- The Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP) is a common architecture for all Sentinel Toolboxes.
- Ideal for Earth observation processing and analysis.
- SNAP and the individual Sentinel Toolboxes support numerous sensors other than Sentinel sensors.
- ESA/ESRIN is providing the SNAP user tool free of charge to the Earth Observation Community.

ESA SNAP

<https://step.esa.int/main/download/snap-download/>

ESA SNAP

Open Sentinel-1 file

ESA SNAP

Visualize VH Amplitude data

ESA SNAP

Subset – Right click for Spatial Subset from View

ESA SNAP

Subset – Right click for Spatial Subset from View

N 45.6836
S 45.5840
E 25.6510
W 25.4148

ESA SNAP

Subset – Export and save product as GeoTIFF

ESA SNAP

• Sentinel-1 preprocessing operations:

1. Speckle filter
2. Calibration
3. Terrain correction
4. Conversion to dB

ESA SNAP

Tool —> Graph builder (define a new graph or load a saved file)

ESA SNAP

Graph builder – Right click to connect graph

ESA SNAP

Graph builder – Run

ESA SNAP

Graph builder – Output

Google Earth Engine

<https://earthengine.google.com/>

Google Earth Engine

https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/COPERNICUS_S1_GRD

Google Earth Engine

Google Earth Engine

International Soil Moisture Network

- ISMN website: <https://ismn.earth/en/>
- International cooperation to establish and maintain a global in-situ soil moisture database. This database is an essential means for validating and improving global satellite products, and land surface, climate, and hydrological models.

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- <https://ismn.earth/en/>
- <https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel/home>

Acknowledgment

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Romanian Excellence Center on Artificial Intelligence in Earth Observation Data for Agriculture

Institutul de Cercetare-Dezvoltare AL UNIVERSITĂȚII TRANSILVANIA DIN BRAȘOV

Universitatea Transilvania din Braşov

Multispectral and Hyperspectral data Use of Optical and Infrared data for applications in agriculture

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9th May 2024

<http://www.rsac1.co.uk/rs.html>

NDVI

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

Compares the reflectance value of the Red and NIR regions of the electromagnetic spectrum

$$-1 < NDVI = \frac{\rho_{nir} - \rho_{red}}{\rho_{nir} + \rho_{red}} < 1$$

- **Green (healthy) vegetation** reflects much of the near infrared light (NIR) and very little of the red light
- **Stressed vegetation** reflects less near infrared light (NIR) and more red light

NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)

NDWI

Normalized Difference Water Index

Compares the reflectance value of the SWIR and NIR regions of the electromagnetic spectrum

$$-1 < NDWI = \frac{\rho_{nir} - \rho_{swir}}{\rho_{nir} + \rho_{swir}} < 1$$

NDWI is calculated with the help of water absorption band (connected with moisture) so, it is sensitive to changes in liquid water content of vegetation leaves

Drought Risk Management -
Macedonia

15/08/2016 vs 17/08/2017

LST

Land Surface Temperature

When the plant is stressed and transpiration decreases, the crop canopy temperature tends to rise appreciably because of the reduction in evaporative cooling. This is the basis for sensing crop stress by monitoring canopy temperature with TIR radiation

Khalife et al.; AJEE, 12(4): 42-51, 2020; Article no. AJEE.57316

EO Logic workflow

Long-Term Grass Biomass Estimation from Satellite Data

End-to-End automatic EO data processing approach exploiting 20-year time series of historical data in significant regions of Africa where food security is a critical problem

Zambia Landsat based Classification

Patches (50 X 50 km) for NDVI MODIS based computation

NDVI Time series

HYPERSPECTRAL DATA

Hyperspectral

Images acquired in many, narrow, contiguous spectral bands throughout visible, near-IR, mid-IR and thermal portions of the spectrum. Enables discrimination among surface features and unique object fingerprinting.

Eg. Hunting new valuable mineral deposits on surface of earth and in space

Multispectral

Discrete measurement of visible and near-infrared spectrum with a limited number of wide bands (typically, 4-7 spectral bands), limited informational content vs hyperspectral

Eg. Generic indexes such as NDVI used in Ag.

<https://medium.com/remote-sensing-in-agriculture/hyperspectral-imaging-in-agriculture-opportunities-benefits-and-future-perspectives-ba112d2b741a>

Better performance in the identification of crop diseases, nutrient deficiencies, type of weeds

Multispectral and hyperspectral data – Use of optical and infrared data for applications in agriculture

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AI4AGRI Summer School 2024, Brasov, Romania
9th May 2024

Remote Sensing data for agriculture

- Precision agriculture.
- Reducing environmental impacts (adaptive inputs, e.g., water and fertilizer, ensured outputs, e.g., crop yield and biomass).
- Crop and soil conditions and attribute retrieval.
- Classification and segmentation of images.
- Monitoring vegetation properties.

Remote Sensing data for agriculture

- Platforms: satellites, UAVs, airplanes, close-range...
- Ground-based measurements are limited to a few numbers of field sites, and they cannot capture spatial variability across large areas.

Multispectral and hyperspectral RS imagery

- Multispectral RS imagery
Collecting spectral signals in a few discrete bands, each spanning a broad spectral range from tens to hundreds of nanometres.
- Hyperspectral RS imaging
Collecting spectral signals in a series of continuous channels with a narrow spectral bandwidth (e.g., typically below 10 nm).

Multispectral imagery for agriculture

- Widely used in agricultural studies to retrieve various crop and soil attributes, such as crop chlorophyll content, biomass, yield, and soil degradation.
- Detection of weed, land use, crop classification.

Hyperspectral imagery for agriculture

- More detailed spectral responses: improved ability to detect fine variations of ground covers and their changes over time, more accurate and timely detection of crop physiological status.
- Monitoring vegetation properties, estimating the Leaf Area Index (LAI), discriminating crop types, retrieving crop biomass, chlorophyll and nitrogen contents, crop water content, pests and disease, plant height, phenological information, soil moisture, and soil organic matter content.

Pros and cons

- **Multispectral imagery:** due to the limitations in spectral resolution, the accuracy of the retrieved variables is often limited, and early signals of crop stresses (e.g., nutrient deficiency, crop disease) cannot be effectively detected in a timely manner.
- **Hyperspectral imagery:** high cost of the sensors and imaging missions, and various technical challenges (e.g., low signal-to-noise ratio and large data volume).
- **Spatial and temporal resolution.**

Remote Sensing for agriculture

- Number of studies focused on agricultural Remote Sensing between 2000 and 2019 by sensor type.

Multispectral satellite missions

Mission (Organization)	Spatial/Temporal resolution	Launch Date	Data availability
Sentinel-2 (ESA)	10-20-60 m / 5 days	23/06/2015	Public
Landsat-9 (USGS, NASA)	15-30 m / 16 days	27/09/2021	Public
MODIS Terra e Aqua (NASA, METI, CSA JAXA, INPE)	250-500-1000 m / 1-2 days	18/09/1999, 04/05/2002	Public
SPOT-7 (CNES)	2-8 m / 1 day	30/06/2014	Commercial

Hyperspectral satellite missions

Mission (Organization)	Spatial/Temporal resolution	30	Data availability
PRISMA (ASI)	30 m / 7 days	22/03/2019	Public
EnMAP (DLR)	30 m / 4 days	01/04/2022	Public
EO-1 Hyperion (NASA)	30 m /	21/11/2000 (EOM ¹ : 03/2017)	Public
PROBA-1 CHRIS (ESA, UK)	17 m / 7 days	22/10/2001 (EOM: 12/2022)	Public

¹ End-Of-Mission

Copernicus and Sentinel missions

- Copernicus is a European program that provide free satellite and in-situ information.
- Sentinel missions are ESA missions based on a constellation of satellites developed within the Copernicus program which provide robust datasets for Copernicus services.

Sentinel-2 mission

- Twin satellites placed in the same orbit, phased at 180° to each other.
- Combined revisit time of 5 days.
- Multispectral images (13 bands) acquired in the visible and infrared.
- Spatial resolution depends on the acquisition band (10, 20, or 60 m).
- Land monitoring, emergency management, security, climate change, marine services.

Sentinel-2 acquisition

- Different processing levels: L-0, L-1A, L-1B, L-1C, L-2A (L-1C and L-2A are distributed to the users).
- Processing steps: bands coregistration, radiometric correction, orthorectification, masks and classification maps.
- L-1C: Bottom-of-Atmosphere Reflectance.
- L-2A: Top-of-Atmosphere Reflectance.

Landsat 9 mission

- Latest satellite in the Landsat series, largely replicates its predecessor Landsat 8.
- Two instruments: Operational Land Imager 2 (OLI-2, visible, near infrared and shortwave-infrared) and Thermal Infrared Sensor 2 (TIRS-2 thermal infrared radiation).
- Combined revisit time with Landsat 8 of 8 days.
- Spatial resolution depends on the acquisition band (15, 30, or 100 m).
- Land monitoring, emergency management, climate change, water use.

Landsat 9 acquisition

- Level 2: atmospherically corrected surface reflectance and surface temperature science products (generated from Level-1 inputs).
- Collection category (Tier): Tier 1 contains the highest quality Level-1 Terrain Precision.

NDVI

- NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) is the most known and used vegetation index for quantifying green vegetation.
- This is a measurement of plant health based on how a plant reflects light at specific frequencies.
- The NDVI calculation normalizes green leaf scattering in the Near Infrared (NIR) wavelength and chlorophyll absorption in the red wavelength (RED).

NDVI

- Chlorophyll strongly absorbs visible light while the cell structure of leaves strongly reflects NIR light.
- When a plant becomes dehydrated, sick, or affected by disease, the plant absorbs more of that NIR light rather than reflecting it.
- When NIR light hits a leaf on a healthy plant, it is reflected back.

NDVI

NDVI

- NDVI calculation:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

$$NDVI(\text{using Sentinel} - 2) = \frac{B8 - B4}{B8 + B4}$$

NDMI

- NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index) is a normalized difference moisture index used to monitor changes in water content of leaves.
- NDMI uses NIR and Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) bands to display moisture.
- The SWIR band reflects changes in both the vegetation water content and the spongy mesophyll structure in vegetation canopies, while the NIR reflectance is affected by leaf internal structure and leaf dry matter content but not by water content.

NDMI

- The combination of the NIR with the SWIR removes variations induced by leaf internal structure and leaf dry matter content, improving the accuracy in retrieving the vegetation water content.

NDMI

- NDMI calculation

$$NDMI = \frac{NIR - SWIR}{NIR + SWIR}$$

$$NDVI(\text{using Sentinel} - 2) = \frac{B8 - B11}{B8 + B11}$$

NDMI vs. NDWI

- NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index) is often used synonymously with the NDMI index, but NIR-SWIR highlighting differences in water content of leaves, and GREEN-NIR highlighting differences in water content of water bodies.

Requirement for the exercise

- S2B_MSIL2A_20230828T090559_N0509_R050_T35TLL_20230828T121048.SAFE.zip input file
- Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem Account
- brasov_ndvi_aoi.kml file
- ESA SNAP Toolboxes
- GEE code link (<https://code.earthengine.google.com/4885d8cde65e36dd1d4354bcb4f8b112>)

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Explore data → Copernicus Browser

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Create an area of interest → Upload a file to create an area of interest

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Create an area of interest → Upload a file to create an area of interest

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Search → Sentinel-2 L2A

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Search → Time range

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Product info → Download

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Visualize NDVI map in the Copernicus Ecosystem

Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

Visualize NDVI map in the Copernicus Ecosystem

ESA SNAP

- The Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP) is a common architecture for all Sentinel Toolboxes.
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- SNAP and the individual Sentinel Toolboxes support numerous sensors other than Sentinel sensors.
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ESA SNAP

<https://step.esa.int/main/download/snap-download/>

ESA SNAP

Open Sentinel-2 file

ESA SNAP

Visualize RGB image – Right-click on the file name

ESA SNAP

Visualize RGB image – Pick red, green, and blue bands

ESA SNAP

Visualize RGB image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – Save NDVI image as GeoTIFF

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – Set NDVI bands

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – Open NDVI image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – Color manipulation of the NDVI image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – Color manipulation of the NDVI image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – Color manipulation of the NDVI image

ESA SNAP

Window → Tile horizontally

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – RGB image and NDVI image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDVI – RGB image and NDVI image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Resampling

ESA SNAP

Resampling

- To calculate indexes using bands acquired with different spatial resolutions, the data need to be with the same spatial resolution for each band. For Sentinel-2 imagery, this intermediate step needs to be applied to the process chain in the case of the NDMI calculation, but not in the case of the NDVI calculation.
- In the resampled image each band is characterized by a spatial resolution as the reference band for the resampling process.

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Resampling

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Resampling

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Band maths

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Band maths

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Band maths

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – Color manipulation of the NDMI image

ESA SNAP

Calculate NDMI – RGB image, NDVI image, NDMI image

ESA SNAP

File → Export → GeoTIFF

Google Earth Engine

<https://earthengine.google.com/>

Google Earth Engine

<https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/landsat-9>

Google Earth Engine

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Romanian Excellence Center on Artificial Intelligence in Earth Observation Data for Agriculture

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Romanian Excellence Center
on
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Institutul de
Cercetare-Dezvoltare
AL UNIVERSITĂȚII
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DIN BRAȘOV

Universitatea
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UAV applications in agriculture

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AI4AGRI Summer School 2024, Brasov, Romania
9th May 2024

Flight height (m)	100	200	300	400	500	600
Picture format width (m)	100	200	300	400	500	600
Picture format length (m)	150	300	450	600	750	900
Coverage area (km²)	0.015	0.06	0.135	0.24	0.375	0.54
GSD (m)	0.027	0.053	0.08	0.107	0.133	0.16

Jing Hei, Yongshu Li, Kake Zhang, Research of UAV Flight Planning Parameters, Positioning, 2012, 3, 43-45

UAV SYSTEMS

- Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, flies without an onboard pilot
- Completely automated (pre-planned flight path) or remotely
- Controlled with a mobile or fixed station
- Vertical take off and landing possibility
- Various type of sensors, more common today applications with Visible and infrared systems
- Centimetric ground spatial resolution

Multi-Rotor

Fixed-Wing

Multi-rotor drones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to control and maneuver • VTOL and hover flight • Often lower price • Portability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited flying time • Small payload capabilities • Less stability in the wind • Lower flight speeds
Fixed-wing drones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer flight time • Can carry a heavier payload • Greater stability in the wind • Higher flight speeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More training needed • No VTOL/hover • Expensive • Difficult to land, more places needed

<https://www.jouav.com/blog/drone-types.html>

Sensor Agricultural Applications

	RGB	NIR	Multispectral	Thermal	LIDAR
Terrain Mapping	x	x	x		x
Soil Management	x	x	x		x
Crop Establishment	x	x	x		
Vegetation Health Monitoring	x	x	x	x	
Disease Detection	x	x	x		
Vegetation Growth and Yield Estimation	x	x	x		x
Irrigation Management	x	x	x	x	
Weed Detection	x	x	x		
Damage Assessment	x	x	x		
Holistic Crop Management	x	x	x	x	x

Most commercially bought drones come with built in RGB sensors. For more specialised sensors, then specific drones capable of carrying them will be required

<https://www.fas.scot/downloads/uavs-in-agriculture-drone-based-agricultural-services/>

PRE-PLANTING

Terrain Mapping

- A RGB sensor can be used to generate a terrain/slope model of the field used as a decision -making tool for seeding and field management
- Crop line planning can be completed up to 75% faster using drone produced topographic maps compared to ground methods
- Topographic maps of the fields can be uploaded to navigation and autopilot systems found on farm vehicles for more accurate and quick ploughing
- Generation of a base layer for calculating crop heights later in the season

<https://www.fas.scot/environment/uavs-in-agriculture/>

PRE-PLANTING

Soil Mapping

- Soil data can be collected that highlight soil compaction, erosion pathways, organic matter
- By using a NIR or Multispectral sensor, different soil types and moisture levels can also be identified

Thematic map of soil organic matter (SOM) remote sensing monitoring (a) and digital elevation model (DEM) image (b) in the study area.

Zhou, J.; Xu, Y.; Gu, X.; Chen, T.; Sun, Q.; Zhang, S.; Fan, Y. High-Precision Mapping of Soil Organic Matter Based on UAV Imagery Using Machine Learning Algorithms. *Drones* 2023, 7, 290

POST-PLANTING

Crop Establishment

- Improve the awareness on the uptake rate of a crop after planting. In near real time, RGB, NIR or Multispectral sensors to complete stand counts, identifying how many plants successfully established themselves
- Mis-plants can be detected to determine where replanting needs to occur and the data collected may be used as evidence for insurance claims conducted by a farmer

MID-SEASON

Vegetation Health Monitoring and Disease Detection

- Ability to quickly and accurately monitor the canopy health of crops, covering larger areas far faster than traditional field walking
- Early detection of potential diseases and pests is key in reducing impacts to the rest of the crop
- Plant health algorithms can be used to create field scale maps of visible crop surfaces highlighting potential deficiencies and disease throughout the field, saving both time and money

Spray Applications

<https://www.fambrite.com/post/innovative-uses-for-drones-in-agriculture>

MID TO LATE-SEASON

Vegetation Growth and Yield Estimation Monitoring growth rate and variability

- Using RGB, NIR or Multispectral sensors, data can be collected at various stages through the crop growth cycle (e.g. just before fertilising the crop), and when coupled with a soil base layer created at the start of the season offers a quick and cost-effective tool for understanding and gauging crop growth and potential yields
- Removal of much of the uncertainty surrounding productivity, allowing farmers to make informed decisions around areas such as future purchasing and planting

https://medium.com/@info_24967/drone-based-plant-health-monitoring-a85c69e4c8d1

Irrigation Management

- Mentioned terrain/slope maps can be helpful also for this activity, highlighting where water might accumulate and where the field may be vulnerable to erosion
- Later in the crop cycle thermal sensors can be used to pick out poor drainage by identifying the temperature difference between wet and dryer soil
- Thermal sensors can also pick out irrigation issues through detecting crop temperature variations, as higher temperatures in crops is an indication of water stress

<https://www.drone-thermal-camera.com/detection-of-water-stress-cereals-crops-with-thermal-camera/>

THROUGHOUT THE YEAR

Weed Detection

Detecting weeds reduces the amount of time needed on field and can highlight areas of weeds that may be missed at eye height when completing crop walks

- Pre-sowing to get rid of weeds prior to planting
- At the establishment phase to identify weed pressure on emerging crop
- Towards the end of crop growth to map areas of weeds for management post-harvest

Damage Assessment and Mitigation

Real-time overview of yield loss due to large and often more extreme weather events

- Improving decision making
- Providing evidence to back up insurance claims
- Get a birds eye view of farm structural damage or livestock locations
- Detecting livestock and any flooding or water pooling that may occur in such situations

THE FUTURE (1)

Insect-size drones capable of pollinating flowers in the same manner as bees

The drones use GPS to select the optimal flight path for pollinating all plants in a given area

As the world faces a crisis in dwindling bee populations, drones may very well become a replacement pollinator

Credit: Nitin J Sanket and University of Maryland DRUM

THE FUTURE (2)

In early 2020, a team in Canada [announced](#) the development of a drone used for planting trees. Using a pressurized air cannon, the team successfully fired small pods of seeds into the ground

The group estimates a single drone operator would be capable of planting 100,000 seed pods per day

<https://www.standard.co.uk/news/world/treeplanting-drones-could-help-restore-world-s-forests-a4116376.html>

WEED DETECTION APPLICATION

- Weeds are a significant factor causing substantial yield losses in major crops, leading to annual global economic losses.
- System for real-time automated weed detection and control in crop fields using Artificial Intelligence (AI), such that this detected location of the weed can be utilised to activate the counter measures to control them.

UAV System Components

WEED-INFERENCE ENGINE

- A Dynamic Neural Network architecture for weed-detection :- Slimmable Unet architecture
- Model was designed and trained using the Pytorch Deep Learning framework

Slimmable Network Concept

TRAINING PHASE

RESULTS

WIDTH	PRECISION
25%	0%
50%	70.42%
75%	73.33%
100%	74.77%

ON-BOARD PROCESSING HARDWARE

AI algorithms require specific, innovative and high-performance hardware

On-board operations require compact and low-power hardware

Intel® Movidius™ Myriad™ X Vision Processing Unit (VPU)

- Space radiation tested
- Specifically developed for AI-based image processing

JETSON NANO

Visualization of Hyperspectral Images

Radu Coliban

AI4AGRI Summer School, Brașov
10.05.2024

Introduction

- Hyperspectral imaging captures high-resolution information in hundreds of spectral bands
- Human interaction with hyperspectral images is important for interpretation and analysis
 - Often the first step in an image analysis chain

1

2

Problem

- Reducing the number of bands to just 3 color channels (Red, Green, Blue) for display
 - Information meaningful from a human point of view

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Solutions

- Many *visualization* techniques have been developed so far:
 - Band selection methods
 - PCA-based techniques
 - Linear approaches
 - AI-based methods
 - ...

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Band selection

- Pick three spectral bands and map them to R, G, B
- Simplest approach: the user picks the bands
- Example criterion: choose the three bands closest to red, green and blue

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Band selection example

- Pavia University has 103 spectral bands covering the 430-860 nm range
- Natural-looking image: we choose three bands, each of them in the B, G and R range, respectively

The colors of the visible light spectrum^[5]

Color	Wavelength interval	Frequency interval
Red	~ 700–635 nm	~ 430–480 THz
Orange	~ 635–590 nm	~ 480–510 THz
Yellow	~ 590–560 nm	~ 510–540 THz
Green	~ 560–520 nm	~ 540–580 THz
Cyan	~ 520–490 nm	~ 580–610 THz
Blue	~ 490–450 nm	~ 610–670 THz
Violet	~ 450–400 nm	~ 670–750 THz

Source: Wikipedia

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Band selection example (2)

- Supposing band wavelengths are equally spaced, the difference between two bands can be approximated as:

$$(860 \text{ nm} - 430 \text{ nm})/102 = 4.21 \text{ nm}$$

- B channel: $430 \text{ nm} + 9 \times 4.21 = 467.89 \text{ nm} \rightarrow$ band 10
- G channel: $430 \text{ nm} + 30 \times 4.21 = 556.3 \text{ nm} \rightarrow$ band 31
- R channel: $430 \text{ nm} + 55 \times 4.21 = 661.55 \text{ nm} \rightarrow$ band 56

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Band selection results

Bands 10, 31, 56

Bands 15, 70, 100

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Advanced band selection

- More advanced approaches select bands automatically
- Example – quality-based band selection*:
 - Apply the BRISQUE image quality metric on each band
 - Select bands corresponding to the three local minima (high quality) from the resulting vector
 - Detail enhancement using the bitonic filter

* R.M. Coliban, M. Ivanovici, "Quality-based Band Selection for Hyperspectral Image Visualization", Remote Sensing Letters, 2023

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Quality-based band selection

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Principal Component Analysis

- Principal components: set of orthogonal vectors that best fit the data, maximizing variance in descending order

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PCA-based visualization

- Simple technique: map three components to R, G, B
 - Usually the first three:

- PCA also used as part of more complex approaches

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Linear methods

- For each color channel, weights are assigned to each spectral band
- Sum the weighted bands = color value
- Weights given by specific functions: color matching functions, spectral sensitivity functions, etc.

$$I_k(x, y) = \sum_{\lambda_{\min}}^{\lambda_{\max}} C_k(\lambda) \cdot R_{(x,y)}(\lambda), k = R, G, B$$

Color value Function Hyperspectral value

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Linear method example*

- Color camera sensor spectral sensitivity functions → similar shape to the spectral sensitivities of human cone cells:

* R.M. Coliban, M. Marincas, C. Hatfaludi, M. Ivanovici, "Linear and Non-Linear Models for Remotely-Sensed Hyperspectral Image Visualization", Remote Sensing, 2020

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Linear method example (2)

- Visualization using Canon 1D and Nikon D50 functions

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AI-based methods

- Techniques that generally rely on extra information for training
 - For instance, a geographically-matched RGB image
- Various methods:
 - Constrained manifold learning
 - Pulse-coupled neural networks
 - Artificial neural networks
 - ...

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ANN*

- Visualization method based on an artificial neural network (ANN)
- Input: spectral curve
- Output: RGB values
- Applied per pixel

* R.M. Coliban, M. Marincas, C. Hatfaludi, M. Ivanovici, "Linear and Non-Linear Models for Remotely-Sensed Hyperspectral Image Visualization", Remote Sensing, 2020

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ANN training

- Spectral reflectance curves of the 24 patches in the McBeth color checker

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ANN visualization

- Natural-looking visualization
- Good results despite reduced training set

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FCNN*

- Fully-Connected Neural Network
- Similar to ANN

* I.C. Plajer, A. Baicoianu, L. Majercsik, M. Ivanovici, "Multisource Remote Sensing Data Visualization Using Machine Learning", IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, 2024

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FCNN training

CAVE Dataset: 32 multispectral images of size 512 x 512 pixels, in indoor environment, spectral range 400 nm - 700 nm in 10 nm intervals => 31 frequencies, RGB equivalent - rendered under CIE Standard Illuminant D65

UGR Dataset: 14 multispectral images, 11 of size 1000 x 900 and 3 of size 900 x 1000 pixels, in outdoor environment, spectral range 400 nm - 1000 nm in 10 nm intervals => 62 frequencies - 31 in the visible domain and 31 in the NIR domain, RGB equivalent - rendered under CIE Standard Illuminant D65

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FCNN results

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Lab: visualization using Octave

- From http://miv.unitbv.ro/ai4agri_vis/ download the **PaviaU.mat** and **Canon1D.mat** files
- In Octave, change Current Directory to saved file location
- Load image:
 - `load('PaviaU.mat');`
 - Check Workspace: the image is stored in the **paviaU** variable of type double and dimension 610 x 340 x 103 (lines x columns x channels)
- Display the value of a pixel in the command line:
 - `paviaU(20, 100, :)`

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Displaying a single band

- Extract channel 70 in a separate variable
 - `ch70 = paviaU(:, :, 70);`
- **ch70** is a 610 x 340 matrix (one channel) → can be displayed as a grayscale image
- Check min and max values in ch70:
 - `min(min(ch70))`
 - `max(max(ch70))`
- If a matrix is the argument, have to call min or max function twice: first, computed on columns, then on the resulting values

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Normalization

- Problem: In order to display an image of type `double`, the pixel values have to be in the `[0, 1]` interval
- Plus: We want to cover the entire intensity range from black to white
- Solution: Normalization → subtract min value from all pixels, then divide by max-min:
 - `ch70 = (ch70 - min(min(ch70))) / (max(max(ch70)) - min(min(ch70))) ;`
- Simpler solution: use `rescale` function
 - `ch70 = rescale(ch70) ;`
- Display the grayscale image:
 - `figure ;`
 - `imshow(ch70) ;`

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Band selection

- We now want to display a color image → it must have three channels
 - Matlab/Octave convention: channel 1 is R, 2 is G, 3 is B
- We select bands 10, 31 and 56
 - `pavia_bs = paviaU(:, :, 56) ;`
 - `pavia_bs(:, :, 2) = paviaU(:, :, 31) ;`
 - `pavia_bs(:, :, 3) = paviaU(:, :, 10) ;`
- Normalize each color channel:
 - `pavia_bs(:, :, 1) = rescale(pavia_bs(:, :, 1)) ;`
 - `pavia_bs(:, :, 2) = rescale(pavia_bs(:, :, 2)) ;`
 - `pavia_bs(:, :, 3) = rescale(pavia_bs(:, :, 3)) ;`
- Display image using `imshow`

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Linear method

- Image matrix has to be converted to an `n x 103` matrix
 - `pavia_temp = reshape(paviaU, 610*340, 103) ;`
- Load Canon 1D spectral sensitivity function matrix:
 - `load('Canon1D.mat') ;`
- Compute color pixel values by matrix multiplication and reshape into color image:
 - `pavia_lin = pavia_temp * canon1D ;`
 - `pavia_lin = reshape(pavia_lin, 610, 340, 3) ;`
- Normalize and display color image

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Conclusions

- Human interaction with hyperspectral images is often an important first stage in processing and analysis
- A series of visualization techniques have been developed for displaying hyperspectral images
- The choice of a particular method depends on the application

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Semantic Segmentation For Agriculture

Corneliu Florea
Brasov
May 2024

Problems in agricultural images

Zhang, H., Liu, M., Wang, Y., Shang, J., Liu, X., Li, B., Song, A. and Li, Q., 2021. Automated delineation of agricultural field boundaries from Sentinel-2 images using recurrent residual U-Net. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 105, p.102557.

Jong, M., Guan, K., Wang, S., Huang, Y., & Peng, B. (2022). Improving field boundary delineation in ResUNets via adversarial deep learning. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 112, 102877.

2

Problems in agricultural images

Plants part identification and segmentation

Mukhamadiev, S., Nesteruk, S., Illarionova, S., & Somov, A. (2023). Enabling multi-part plant segmentation with instance-level augmentation using weak annotations. *Information*, 14(7), 380.

Xia, C., Wang, L., Chung, B. K., & Lee, J. M. (2015). In situ 3D segmentation of individual plant leaves using a RGB-D camera for agricultural automation. *Sensors*, 15(8), 20463-20479.

3

Problems in agricultural images

Plant disease localization

Nawaz, M., Nazir, T., Javed, A., Masood, M., Rashid, I., Kim, J., & Husain, A. (2022). A robust deep learning approach for tomato plant leaf disease localization and classification. *Scientific reports*, 12(1), 18568.

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Preliminary conclusion

- Precision/ Digital agriculture needs and may use many automatic, machine learning/based solution to improve
- Overview of computer vision taxonomy
 - Problem and standard solutions

Computer vision problems

Fei-Fei Li & Andrej Karpathy & Justin Johnson

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SuperPIXels

Non deep learning

Image segmentation

Goal: Group pixels into meaningful or perceptually similar regions

What is the superpixel?

- A cluster of connected pixels with similar features (ex: color , brightness , texture...).
- It can be regarded as a result of over segmentation.
- The concept was proposed in 2003 but the results of some former methods also can be called superpixels. (ex: watershed, mean shift)

Watershed [1]

TurboPixel [2]

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Desirable Properties of Superpixels

- Good adherence to object boundaries
- Regular shape and similar size
- Compute fast and simple to use

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Superpixel Methods

- **Graph-based:** Superpixel Lattice, Efficient Graph-based segmentation, Ncut, ERS.....
- **Gradient-based:** Watershed, MeanShift, Quick-Shift, TurboPixel, **SLIC**.....

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Simulation Results

- Regular and compact superpixel
- Fast and simple

The average superpixel size in the upper left of each image is 100 pixels and is 300 in the lower right.

[6] Achanta, Radhakrishna, et al. "SLIC superpixels compared to state-of-the-art superpixel methods."

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Segmentation for efficiency: "superpixels"

SLIC (Achanta et al. PAMI 2012)

1. Initialize cluster centers on pixel grid in steps S
- Features: Lab color, x-y position
2. Move centers to position in 3x3 window with smallest gradient
3. Compare each pixel to cluster center within 25 pixel distance and assign to nearest
4. Recompute cluster centers as mean color/position of pixels belonging to each cluster
5. Stop when residual error is small

- + Fast 0.36s for 320x240
- + Regular superpixels
- + Superpixels fit boundaries
- May miss thin objects
- Large number of superpixels

http://infoscience.epfl.ch/record/177415/files/Superpixel_PAMI2011-2.pdf

Superpixel on Remote sensing imaging

Multispectral

Deep Learning

Classification AND localization

Conv Nets

Classification + Localization

Classification: C classes
Input: Images
Output: Class Label
Performance metric: Accuracy

→ CAT

Localization:
Input: Image
Output: Rectangle in the image (x, y, w, h)
Performance metric: Intersection over Union

→ (x, y, w, h)

Classification and Localization are done simultaneously

Fei-Fei Li & Andrej Karpathy & Justin Johnson

Idea: Localization as regression

• Localization by regression

Localization by regression

Localization by regression

Multiple - k - objects

Sliding window

Steps:

- Runs the network (classification + regression) to multiple locations on a high resolution image
- Combine the classifier and regressor predictions at all scales for the final prediction

Sliding window

Overfeat

Overfeat

Sermanet, P., Eigen, D., Zhang, X., Mathieu, M., Fergus, R., & LeCun, Y. (2013). Overfeat: Integrated recognition, localization and detection using convolutional networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6229*.

Overfeat

Sermanet, P., Eigen, D., Zhang, X., Mathieu, M., Fergus, R., & LeCun, Y. (2013). Overfeat: Integrated recognition, localization and detection using convolutional networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6229*.

Overfeat

Sermanet, P., Eigen, D., Zhang, X., Mathieu, M., Fergus, R., & LeCun, Y. (2013). Overfeat: Integrated recognition, localization and detection using convolutional networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6229*.

Region proposal

- An agnostic classifier is trained to look for blob regions that can be potential objects
- Its purpose is not to find objects but promising regions
- Proposals with IoU > 50% are positive
- Fixed proportion of positive examples in each batch

R-CNN

R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, J. Malik CVPR, 2014 "Rich Feature Hierarchies for Accurate Object Detection and Semantic Segmentation" CVPR 2014

R-CNN

Semantic segmentation

Mottaghi, R., Chen, X., Liu, X., Cho, N. G., Lee, S. W., Fidler, S., ... & Yuille, A. (2014). The role of context for object detection and semantic segmentation in the wild. In *CVPR* (pp. 891-898).

Legend: Layers in segmentation architectures

Deconvolution Layer

Deconvolution layer = convolution transposed

output
input

AKA: **convolution with subunitary stride**
https://github.com/vdmoulin/conv_arithmetic

Inputs with blue albastru outputs with cyan

Deconvolution with stride

No bordering, supraunitary stride, transposed

Bordered, supraunitary stride, transposed

DeepLab

Deep Lab for segmentation

<http://liangchiehchen.com/projects/DeepLab.html>

It uses pre-trained VGG-16 from which the fully-connected layers are removed

The result is a heat-map obtained by downsampling the segmented image

The final result, at the image resolution, is obtained by bilinear interpolation.

Fully Convolutional Network - FCN

- trainable up-sampling
- Output of the FCN-32s is 1/32 from the input

J. Long, E. Shelhamer, and T. Darrell, "Fully Convolutional Networks for Semantic Segmentation," *IEEE Trans. PAMI.*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 640-651, Nov. 2014.

U-Net

Contracting

Expanding

O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation," *Miccai*, vol. 9351, no. Pt 1, pp. 234-241, May 2015.

U-Net

Each step in the expanding area consists of a sampling followed by a 2x2 convolution (up-convolution) that halves the depth, a concatenation with the corresponding cropped feature map from the contracting area, and two 3x3 convolutions, each followed by a ReLU. Clipping is necessary due to the loss of pixels at the edges in each convolution. At the final level, a 1x1 convolution is used to transform each 64-component vector into the desired number of classes.

SegNet

Replaces *up-sampling* with **un-pooling** by storing the position of the max value

Badrinarayanan, V., Kendall, A., & Cipolla, R. (2017). Segnet: A deep convolutional encoder-decoder architecture for image segmentation. *IEEE T PAMI*, 39(12), 2481-2495.

Un-pooling

- Remember (store) the max positions.
- In unpooling, place the max value in the stored position

Zeiler and Fergus Deconv-net Ecvv 2014

DeepLab_V3

- Atrous Convolution = Dilated Convolution

https://github.com/vdumoulin/conv_arithmetic

DeepLab_V3

Figure 3. Cascaded modules without and with atrous convolution.

DeepLab_V3

Chen, L. C., Papandreou, G., Schroff, F., & Adam, H. (2017). Rethinking atrous convolution for semantic image segmentation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1706.05587*.

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Losses in segmentation

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Common losses

Two commonly used loss functions

Cross Entropy (CE)

$$D_{KL}(p \parallel q) = H(p, q) - H(p)$$

Entropy
Cross entropy

Distribution-based Loss

Dice

$$Dice\ loss = 1 - \frac{2|G \cap S|}{|G| + |S|}$$

Region-based Loss

Jun Ma "Loss Functions for Medical Image Segmentation: A Taxonomy" <https://miccai-sb.github.io/materials/Ma2019.pdf>

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Many other losses

Ma, J., Chen, J., Ng, M., Huang, R., Li, Y., Li, C., ... & Martel, A. L. (2021). Loss odyssey in medical image segmentation. *Medical Image Analysis*, 71, 102035.

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SAR Image Data Processing and Analysis

Yajing Yan

AI4AGRI Summer School

May 10, 2024

- 1 SAR images
- 2 Offset tracking
- 3 Interferometry SAR
- 4 Multi-temporal InSAR
- 5 New research directions in InSAR
- 6 Machine learning & SAR applications

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SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) image acquisition

Satellite SAR imagery: taking images from space by sensors placed on satellites

Active sensors:

- Electromagnetic wave at microwave frequency
- Day and night (independent of the sun)
- All-weather capability (ability to pass through clouds)

⇒ Systematic and regular acquisitions, free and timely access

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SAR image acquisition

Band	Wavelength	Satellites	Characteristic & applications
X	2,4 - 3,75 cm	COSMO-SkyMed, TerraSAR-X, PAZ	military use, mapping and monitoring
C	3,75 - 7,5 cm	ERS, ENVISAT, RADARSAT, Sentinel-1, Harmony	surface observation, sea-ice monitoring
S	7,5 - 15 cm	NISAR	weather application, airport monitoring
L	15 - 30 cm	SEASAT, NISAR, ALOS	vegetation observation, glacier/ice cap monitoring
P	30 - 100 cm	BIOMASS	experimental research & applications

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Image SAR

Single Look Complex (SLC) - complex signal: $z = Ae^{j\phi}$

- Amplitude: backscattering intensity
 - wavelength, polarization, incident angle
 - soil properties (topography, roughness, humidity, etc.)
- Phase: geometric information
 - object - sensor distance
 - backscatter properties (random and inaccessible)

Offset tracking

TerraSAR-X (high resolution)

Sentinel-1 (medium resolution)

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Offset tracking

Cross correlation of amplitude between a pair of coregistered images

$$D_{(\hat{h}_1, \hat{h}_2)}^{znc}(\rho, q) = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in \Omega_{(k,l)}} ((h_1(i,j) - \bar{h}_1) \cdot (h_2(i + \rho, j + q) - \bar{h}_2))}{\sqrt{\sum_{(i,j) \in \Omega_{(k,l)}} |h_1(i,j) - \bar{h}_1|^2 \sum_{(i,j) \in \Omega_{(k,l)}} |h_2(i + \rho, j + q) - \bar{h}_2|^2}}$$

$$(\hat{\rho}, \hat{q}) = \operatorname{argmax} D_{(\hat{h}_1, \hat{h}_2)}^{znc}$$

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Offset tracking

Example of TerraSAR-X images for Alpin glacier monitoring

29/09/2008

21/10/2008

déplacement (rg)

déplacement (az)

- Bidimensional displacement measurements (range and azimuth directions of SAR acquisitions)
- Accuracy on the order of $\frac{1}{10}$ pixel
- Efficient for large displacement (earthquake, glacier, etc.)

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Offset tracking

Zero Mean Normalized Cross Correlation

Master window size:

- 21 × 21
- 41 × 41
- 61 × 61
- 81 × 81
- 101 × 101
- 121 × 121

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Offset tracking

Impact of the master window size:

(c) standard deviation

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Offset tracking

Impact of the resolution:

Landsat 30 m

Landsat 15 m

SPOT 10 m

The higher/finer the image resolution, the better the offset tracking results.

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Offset tracking

Attempt to use deep learning

- TerraSAR-X and Sentinel-1 images
- Preliminary results not always consistent with other traditional methods

Shen et al. 2022, Glacier motion monitoring using a novel deep matching network with SAR intensity images.

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Interferometry SAR

SAR Interferometry principle

Young double slit experiment:

SAR interferometry uses this effect of path difference between 2 waves emitted by satellites

- monochromatic source
- diffraction by the slit S_0
- diffraction by the slit S_1 and S_2 : 2 coherent beams
- series of fringes on the screen

Credit: C. Doubre

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SAR Interferometry principle

Prerequisite: two coregistered SLCs (in the same geometry) → remove the random phase component

SAR Interferometry (InSAR)

- Interferogram:

$$\gamma e^{j\varphi}(i,j) = \frac{\sum_{i,j \in \Omega} z_1(i,j) z_2^*(i,j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i,j \in \Omega} z_1(i,j) z_1^*(i,j) \sum_{i,j \in \Omega} z_2(i,j) z_2^*(i,j)}}$$

Ω : multi-looking window (spatial average)

- ▶ coherence $\gamma \in [0, 1]$
- ▶ interferometric phase $\varphi = \phi_1 - \phi_2$, $\varphi \in [-\pi, \pi]$

phase

coherence

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Decorrelation mechanism

$$\gamma = \gamma_N \cdot \gamma_G \cdot \gamma_T$$

- γ_N :
 - ▶ thermal decorrelation
 - ▶ related to the thermal noise of the instrument
- γ_G :
 - ▶ spatial decorrelation
 - ▶ related to acquisition geometry changes (incident angle, etc.)
- γ_T :
 - ▶ temporal decorrelation
 - ▶ related to surface changes (vegetation, snow, etc.)

⇒ InSAR does not work everywhere !

Interferogram denoising & coherence estimation

State-of-the-art

- Boxcar
- Non Local InSAR (Sica et al. 2017, Deledalle et al. 2015)
- Neural Networks (residual learning): e.g. ϕ -Net

Sica et al. 2020, ϕ -Net: deep residual learning for InSAR parameters estimation.

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Differential SAR interferometry (D-InSAR)

Original interferometry

$$\varphi = \varphi_{orb} + \varphi_{topo} + \varphi_{def} + \varphi_{atm} + \varphi_{noise}$$

- φ_{orb} : orbital phase
 - correction with auxiliary orbit data
- φ_{topo} : topographical phase
 - correction with a Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

Differential Interferogram

$$\varphi_d = \varphi_{def} + \varphi_{atm} + \varphi_{noise}$$

- φ_{def} : phase related to surface displacement
- φ_{atm} : atmospheric phase
 - correction with GNSS data, meteorological model, DEM, etc.
- φ_{noise} : phase related to decorrelation noise
 - reduction with filtering

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Differential interferogram

Credit: Q. Dumont

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Atmospheric phase

Tropospheric phase:

Ionospheric phase:

Hu et al. 2019, An accurate method to correct atmospheric phase delay for InSAR with ERA5 Global Atmospheric model.
Zhang et al. 2022, A review of methods for mitigating ionospheric artifacts in differential SAR interferometry.

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Atmospheric phase

ARU-Net

a) d) original interferograms, b) e) corrected by GACOS, c) f) corrected by ARU-Net

Chen et al. 2021, ARU-Net: reduction of atmospheric phase screen in SAR interferometry using attention-based deep residual U-Net.

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Phase unwrapping

$$\varphi = \phi - 2k\pi \quad \text{with } \varphi \in [-\pi, \pi]$$

k the unknown wrap count (also called ambiguity number)

- An ill-posed inverse problem
- Phase continuity assumption (the absolute phase difference between any two neighboring pixels is smaller than π)

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Phase unwrapping

Phase continuity condition

$$\hat{\Delta}(s, s-1) = \begin{cases} 0 & |\phi(s) - \phi(s-1)| \leq \pi \\ -1 & \phi(s) - \phi(s-1) > \pi \\ 1 & \phi(s) - \phi(s-1) < -\pi \end{cases}$$

Almost all the 2D phase unwrapping methods can be considered as a kind of criterion which minimizes the difference between the unwrapped phase gradient and that estimated by the equation above to achieve the PU solution.

Generalized mathematical model

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{k(s)} \sum_{(s,s-1)} f(k(s) - k(s-1) - \Delta(s, s-1))$$

$$k(s) \in \text{integer}$$

f generalized objective function, e.g. L^1 -norm, L^2 -norm.

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Phase unwrapping

Category	Subcategory	Method	Learning objective	Post-processing	Interferogram size
Path following PU	Residue estimation	PGNet	phase gradient	MCF	large
		CNN	phase gradient	wrap count reconstruction	large
	Branch cut	BCNet	branch cut	branch-cut method	large
Global PU	One-step PU	DNN	unwrapped phase	no	small
		DLPU	unwrapped phase	no	small
		PUNet	unwrapped phase	no	small
	Two-step PU	segmentation and denoised network	wrap count	phase jump identification and correction	small
		DeepLabv3+	wrap count	phase jump identification and correction	small
		PhaseNet	wrap count	clustering-based smoothness	small
		PhaseNet 2.0	wrap count	no	small

Zhou et al. 2021, Artificial intelligence in interferometric synthetic aperture radar phase unwrapping

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Phase unwrapping - PGNet

The problem is reformulated as a three-class (0, 1, -1) classification problem.

- First step: get the phase gradient estimation using neural networks

- Second step: get the absolute phase based on the generalized mathematical model

Zhou et al. 2020, Deep convolutional neural network-based robust phase gradient estimation for two-dimensional phase unwrapping using SAR interferograms.

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Phase unwrapping

The problem is reformulated as a five-class (0, ±1/2, ±1) classification problem.

$$\Delta k(s) = \begin{cases} k(s+1) - k(s) & s \text{ leftmost} \\ k(s) - k(s-1) & s \text{ rightmost} \\ (k(s) - k(s-1))/2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Sica et al. 2020, A CNN-based coherence-driven approach for InSAR phase unwrapping.

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2-pass Interferometry SAR

Routine tool for small surface displacement measurement

Advantages

- Large spatial coverage (a few hundred kilometers)
 - High accuracy (cm level displacement)
 - Regular acquisitions and free access of medium resolution SAR images
- High resolution SAR acquisitions are still on demand.

Limitations

- Decorrelation noise
- Atmospheric perturbations
- Monodirectional displacement (line of sight of satellite)

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Complementarity between InSAR and offset tracking

Example of the Kashmir earthquake in 2005:

red: fault; blue: InSAR; yellow: offset tracking; green: both.

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3D displacement estimation

Geometrical modeling:

$$R = PU$$

with R vector of displacement in LOS or azimuth directions, U vector of 3D displacement (E-W, N-S, vertical), P projection matrix.

$$P_{LOS} = (-\cos\alpha \sin\theta, \sin\alpha \sin\theta, -\cos\theta)$$

$$P_{az} = (\sin\alpha, \cos\alpha, 0)$$

The solution is given by

$$U = (P^t \Sigma_R^{-1} P)^{-1} P^t \Sigma_R^{-1} R$$

* Satellite trajectory projected on the ground.

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3D displacement estimation

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Multi-temporal InSAR

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Multi-temporal InSAR

Objectives

- Getting around the limitations of the 2-Pass InSAR method
 - decorrelation noise
 - atmospheric perturbation
- Making best use of available SAR image time series to improve the displacement measurement accuracy
 - cm/year \rightarrow mm/year

Principle

- The development of multi-temporal InSAR methods relies on the way in which temporal decorrelation is taken into account.
- The analysis of the backscattering properties of SAR images is essential.
- The fundamental idea: building interferometric networks from a time series of SAR images.

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Backscatter behaviors

(a) distributed scatterers (b) permanent scatterers

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Backscatter behaviors

INTERFEROMETRIC SYNTHETIC APERTURE RADAR An Introduction for Users of InSAR Data, 2010, <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:14176267>

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Multi-temporal InSAR Approaches

- Permanent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI):
 - processing of temporally coherent point wise scatterers
 - working on full resolution interferograms
 - many variants (Ferretti et al. 2001, Hooper et al. 2007, Kampes 2006)
- Distributed Scatterer Interferometry (DSI):
 - processing of distributed scatterers
 - working on spatially averaged interferograms
 - many variants
 - ★ Phase linking (Guarnieri et Tebaldini, 2008), Robust Phase Linking (Vu et al. 2023), Integer Least-Square (Samiei-Esfahany et al. 2016), EMI (Ansari et al. 2018), CAESAR (Fornaro et al. 2015),
 - ★ SBAS (Berardino et al. 2002, Lanari et al.2004, Doin et al. 2011), Multi-link (Pinel-Puysségur et al. 2012),
 - ★ Principal Mode (Prébet et al. 2019)
- Approches hybrides: STAMPS (Hooper, 2008), SqueeSAR (Ferretti et al. 2011)

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Interferometric networks

(a) PSI (b) PM (Prébet et al. 2019) (c) SBAS, Multi-link (d) Phase linking, Integer Least-Square, EMI

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Phase closure

Interferogram

$$\gamma e^{j\varphi}(i, j) = \frac{\sum_{i, j \in \Omega} z_1(i, j) z_2^*(i, j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i, j \in \Omega} z_1(i, j) z_1^*(i, j) \sum_{i, j \in \Omega} z_2(i, j) z_2^*(i, j)}}$$

Phase closure

$$\varphi_{mn} = \varphi_{om} - \varphi_{on}$$

m, n, o 3 different dates

- The condition of the phase closure is always respected in full resolution (single look) - PSI
- This is not necessarily the case in the case of multi-looked interferograms (with spatial averaging) - DSI

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Phase disclosure

Sources of phase disclosure

- Decorrelation noise
- Short-lived fading signal (related to physical properties of the observed targets such as vegetation, soil moisture)

Maghsoudi et al. 2023, Towards a universally applicable phase bias correction for short-term multi-looked interferograms: challenges and progress.

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Phase disclosure

Phase closure time series vs NDVI

Maghsoudi et al. 2023, Towards a universally applicable phase bias correction for short-term multi-looked interferograms: challenges and progress.

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Common idea - to retrieve the phase closure

PSI & DSI

- PSI: respect the phase closure naturally
→ interferometric network without redundancy (common master) is sufficient
- PM: tends towards the phase closure with the help of a principal component analysis
- SBAS/PL: recover the phase closure using a redundant (wrapped or unwrapped) interferometric network
→ to obtain a common master interferometric network as in PSI

Hybrid approaches

- Step 1: Selection of PS and DS separately
- Step 2: DS with phase closure \equiv PS
- Step 3: Combination DS & PS in a PSI processing

Permanent Scatterer Interferometry

Permanent scatterer selection:

Criteria: high phase stability and reflectivity values:

$$D_a = \frac{\sigma_a}{\bar{a}} \leq \lambda_1$$

$$\bar{a} \geq \lambda \bar{A}$$

D_a amplitude dispersion index, \bar{a} average amplitude, σ_a amplitude standard deviation of the pixel under consideration, \bar{A} average amplitude of all pixels. λ_1 and λ_2 , two threshold values.

- Double bounce scattering
- Man-made structures (buildings, roads, dams, ...)
- For natural areas: corner reflectors

Lazecik et al. 2015, Potential of satellite InSAR techniques for monitoring of bridge deformations.

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Permanent Scatterer Interferometry

Displacement modeling:

$$\phi^m = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \frac{B_{\perp}}{R \sin \theta} h + \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} v T$$

λ wavelength of the radar signal, B_{\perp} perpendicular baseline, θ incidence angle, h DEM error, T temporal baseline, v linear displacement velocity.

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N e^{j(\phi_k^m - \phi_k)}$$

The solution (v, h) is given by maximising the temporal coherence defined above.

- Local 2D regression in the space of (B_{\perp}, T) between nearby PS points $\rightarrow (\delta h, \delta v)$ across arcs linking PS points.
- Spatial integration to get a global solution
- Temporal phase unwrapping (phase consistency condition is met)
- Necessary to check phase standard deviation and residual (large standard deviation related to nonlinear motion)
- Iterative processing chain

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Permanent Scatterer Interferometry

Pros

- High accuracy (mm/year)
- No degradation of the spatial resolution
- Point wise displacement measurements (important for urban infrastructure monitoring)

Cons

- Iterative complex processing chain (difficult to follow the error propagation)
- Linear velocity is considered in the displacement model
- Depends on PS density (weak density in natural areas)

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Distributed Scatterer Interferometry - Small BAseLine Subset

Key features: using only SAR image pairs separated by small temporal and spatial baselines

Displacement modeling on an interferogram

$$\delta\phi \approx \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \delta d_{def} + \frac{B_{\perp}}{R \sin \theta} h + \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \delta d_{atm} + \Delta n$$

δd_{def} phase induced by surface deformation between the two acquisitions, δd_{atm} atmospheric phase artifacts, Δn decorrelation noise.

Pixel-by-Pixel temporal analysis

A system of linear equations by using a matrix formalism

$$A\phi = \delta\phi$$

with A an incident-like matrix

A singular value decomposition inversion gives the minimum norm least-square solution of the system.

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Distributed Scatterer Interferometry - Small BAseLine Subset

Ansari et al. 2020, Study of systematic bias in measuring surface deformation with SAR interferometry.

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Distributed Scatterer Interferometry - Phase linking

For a given pixel x_i , there are N temporal observations:

$$x_i = [x_i^1, x_i^2, \dots, x_i^N]^T$$

A homogeneous neighborhood (similar statistical and backscattering properties): $\Omega = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^L$

Second-order statistic: $E[x^q(x^l)^H] = \gamma_{q,l} \sigma_q \sigma_l e^{j(\theta_q - \theta_l)}$
in matrix form

$$\mathbb{E}[xx^H] \triangleq C = \text{ediag}(w_{\theta}) \underbrace{((\sigma\sigma^T) \circ \Gamma)}_{\Psi} \text{ediag}(w_{\theta})^H$$

Possible solutions:

- Maximum likelihood estimator
- Covariance fitting

with $w_{\theta} = [e^{j\theta_1}, \dots, e^{j\theta_N}]$

$$C(\Psi, \theta) = \text{mod}(C) \odot \arg(C) \triangleq \Psi \odot (w_{\theta} w_{\theta}^H)$$

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Phase linking - Maximum Likelihood

The **Maximum likelihood estimator** corresponds to solutions of the following minimization problem

$$\min_{\Psi, w_{\theta}} \mathcal{L}(C(\Psi, \theta))$$

under the constraint Ψ symmetric and real
 $\theta_0 = 0$

Gaussian data, $x \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, C)$

$$\mathcal{L}_G(C) \propto \text{Tr}\{C^{-1}S\} + \log|C| + \text{const.}$$

with $S = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L x_i x_i^H$.

Non gaussian data, $x_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \tau_i C)$, $\forall i \in [1, L]$

$$\mathcal{L}_{SG}(C) \propto \sum_{i=1}^L \left[\frac{x_i^H C^{-1} x_i}{\tau_i} + \log|\tau_i C| \right] + \text{const.}$$

Vu et al. 2023, Robust phase linking in InSAR.

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Phase linking - Maximum Likelihood

Non gaussian distribution & low rank structure

Sentinel-1 data over the Mexico City

Phase linking - Maximum Likelihood

Vu et al. 2023, Robust phase linking in InSAR.

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Phase linking - covariance fitting

The problem is reformulated as

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}_\theta} d^2(\tilde{\mathbf{C}}, \tilde{\Psi} \odot \mathbf{w}_\theta \mathbf{w}_\theta^H)$$

under the constraint $\theta_1 = 0$

with $\tilde{\Psi} = \text{mod}(\tilde{\mathbf{C}})$, $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ a plug-in estimator of \mathbf{C} and d a matrix divergence.

Possible solutions:

Matrix distance d :

- Kullback - Leibler divergence
- Frobenius norm (least squares)

Plug-in estimator $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$:

- Sample covariance
- M-estimator
- Phase-only matrix ($re^{j\phi} \rightarrow e^{j\phi}$)

Possible solutions:

Regularization:

- Low rank
- Banding
- Shrinkage

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\beta) = \beta \hat{\mathbf{C}} + (1 - \beta) \frac{\text{tr}(\hat{\mathbf{C}})}{p} \mathbf{I}$$

with $\beta \in [0, 1]$.

Bai et al. 2023, LaMIE: large-dimensional multipass InSAR phase estimation for distributed scatterers.
Vu et al. submitted, Covariance fitting interferometric phase linking: modular framework and optimization algorithms.

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Phase linking - covariance fitting

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Phase linking - covariance fitting

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Phase linking summary

- Make use of the full covariance matrix of SAR images
- Provide a mathematical framework for displacement estimation in the statistical sense.
 - ▶ Data distribution (e.g. gaussian, generalized gaussian, etc.)
 - ▶ Covariance structure (e.g. toeplitz, low rank) related to the temporal decorrelation mechanism
- Get around of the short-lived fading signals present in small baselines interferograms.

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How to choose multi-temporal InSAR approaches?

- Comparable performance in most studies
- Particularity of each approach

New research directions in InSAR community

Current research directions

- Establish monitoring systems on a regional, national, even global scale, thanks to the regular and free acquisitions of Sentinel-1 data (e.g. PS deformation map covering the France provided by Altamira)
- Automate processing chains and offer online services to make it easier for non-experts to use the tools (G-TEP, ASF-Vertex, FLATSIM, etc.)
- Development of multi-temporal InSAR methods for operational monitoring
- Deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) in InSAR processing

Operational multi-temporal InSAR

Sequential estimator

- 1 One mini-stack is processed with MLE phase linking and compressed by estimation of the underlying low rank signal subspace.
- 2 The compressed SLC of the first mini-stack is connected to a new mini-stack by generating artificial interferograms.
- 3 MLE phase linking is applied to the new mini-stack.
- 4 The new mini-stack is compressed and archived similar to the initial sequence.
- 5 A datum connection step is performed to provide a single fully connected phase series.

Ansari et al. 2017, Sequential estimator: toward efficient InSAR time series analysis.

Sequential phase linking

How to efficiently integrate new data?

2 frameworks:

	MLE	Cov fitting
image by image	✓	✗
block by block	✗	✓

Sequential estimation

MLE, image by image:

New covariance:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C} &= \text{diag}(\tilde{w}_\theta) \tilde{\Psi} \text{diag}(\tilde{w}_\theta)^H \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} C & \\ \gamma \text{diag}(w_\theta)^H \exp(j\theta_{p+1}) & \text{diag}(w_\theta) \gamma^T \exp(-j\theta_{p+1}) \\ & \gamma_{p+1,p+1} \end{pmatrix} \\ \tau_i \tilde{C} &= \tau_i (\text{diag}(\tilde{w}_\theta) \tilde{\Psi} \text{diag}(\tilde{w}_\theta)^H) \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \tau_i C & \\ \tau_i (\gamma \text{diag}(w_\theta)^H \exp(j\theta_{p+1})) & \tau_i (\text{diag}(w_\theta) \gamma^T \exp(-j\theta_{p+1})) \\ & \tau_i (\gamma_{p+1,p+1}) \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Parameters to estimate: $w_{\theta_{p+1}} = \exp(j\theta_{p+1})$, γ , $\gamma_{p+1,p+1}$, τ_i

El Hajjar et al. 2024, Sequential phase linking: progressive integration of SAR images for operational phase estimation.

Sequential estimation

Cov fitting, block by block:

$$\tilde{\Psi} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\Psi}_{\text{past}} & A^T \\ A & B \end{pmatrix}_{(p+k, p+k)} \quad \tilde{C} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{C}_{\text{past}} & V^H \\ V & Z \end{pmatrix}_{(p+k, p+k)}$$

Frobenius norm, sample covariance as plug-in estimator:

$$\begin{aligned} d_F^2(\tilde{C}, \tilde{\Psi} \circ W_{\theta} W_{\theta}^H) &= -2W_{\theta}^H (\tilde{\Psi} \circ \tilde{C}) W_{\theta} \\ &= -2(W_{\text{past}}^H (\tilde{\Psi}_{\text{past}} \circ \tilde{C}_{\text{past}}) W_{\text{past}} + W_{\text{past}}^H (A^T \circ V^H) W_{\text{new}} \\ &\quad + W_{\text{new}}^H (A \circ V) W_{\text{past}} + W_{\text{new}}^H (B \circ Z) W_{\text{new}}) \end{aligned}$$

Optimization:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{W_{\text{new}}} \quad & d_F^2(\tilde{C}, \tilde{\Psi} \circ W_{\theta} W_{\theta}^H) \\ \text{under the constraint} \quad & W_{\text{new}} \in \mathbb{T}_k \\ & \theta_1 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

El Hajjar et al. in preparation.

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InSAR applications

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Automatic deformation detection

State-of-the-art for automatic deformation detection on interferograms

Data types

- Wrapped interferograms (simulation, real data, long-term/short-term deformation)
- Unwrapped interferograms (simulation, real data, long-term/short-term deformation)

Learning method

- Transfer learning (fine-tuning)
- Supervised learning from scratch
- Self supervised learning

Problem statement

- Classification
- Denoising
- object detection

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: edge detection, wrapped interferograms, transfer learning, real data (more than 30 000 interferograms over 900 volcanos)

Anantrasrichai et al. 2018, Application of machine learning to classification of volcanic deformation in routinely generated InSAR data.

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: edge detection (classification), wrapped interferograms, transfer learning, real data (more than 30 000 interferograms over 900 volcanos)

Anantrasrichai et al. 2018, Application of machine learning to classification of volcanic deformation in routinely generated InSAR data.

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: classification, wrapped interferograms, transfer learning, synthetic data

Anantrasrichai et al. 2019, A deep learning approach to detecting volcano deformation from satellite imagery using synthetic datasets.

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: classification, wrapped interferograms, transfer learning, synthetic data

Anantrasrichai et al. 2019, A deep learning approach to detecting volcano deformation from satellite imagery using synthetic datasets.

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: denoising, unwrapped interferograms, synthetic and real data

Zhu et al. 2024, Deep learning-based coseismic deformation estimation from InSAR interferograms.

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: denoising, unwrapped interferograms, synthetic and real data

Zhu et al. 2024, Deep learning-based coseismic deformation estimation from InSAR interferograms.

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Automatic deformation detection

Example: self supervised contrastive learning, classification, wrapped interferograms, real data

Bountos et al. 2022, Self-supervised contrastive learning for volcanic unrest detection.

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Land cover mapping

State of the art for land cover mapping

Data types

- Optical images (e.g. Landsat 8, Sentinel 2)
- SAR intensity images
- InSAR temporal covariance

Methods

- Traditional machine learning
 - Random forest
 - Support vector machine
 - K-Nearest-Neighbor
- Convolutional neural networks

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Land cover mapping based on interferometric coherence

Flowchart of land cover classification from InSAR temporal coherence

Giffard-Roisin et al. 2022

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Land cover mapping based on interferometric coherence

a) Google Map b) Corine landcover map c) SVM result d) CNN result e) Theia landcover map
Giffard-Roisin et al., 2022, Land cover classification of the Alps from InSAR temporal coherence matrices.

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Geophysical parameters estimation

Context

- Inverse problem: to estimate unobservable physical parameters that are sources of observed data
- State of the art:
 - ▶ Analytical approaches: need for analytical expression
 - ▶ Bayesian approaches (e.g. MCMC): computationally expensive

Motivations

- Deep learning allowing for the development of new solutions for inverse problems in geophysics.
- An ideal framework for integrating physical knowledge into neural network models.

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Problem statement

Estimation of glacier thickness from surface flow velocity measurements

Adapté de Maisch, 1993.

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Study area & data

Data type	Spatial resolution
average surface velocity	50 m
digital elevation model	10 m
GPR ice thickness measurement	10 m

GPR: Ground Penetrating Radar

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Surface velocity example

Millan et al., 2022, Ice velocity and thickness of the world's glaciers.

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Ice thickness measurement example

Grab et al., 2021, Ice thickness distribution of all swiss glaciers based on extended ground-penetrating radar data and glaciological modeling.

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Model architecture - ResNet

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Data preparation & experiment setup

Parameters:

- Manual preparation: 451 glaciers for training, 455 glaciers for validation, 494 glaciers for testing
- Patch size: 400 m × 400 m
- Loss: MAE (Mean Absolute Error)

Experiments:

- Baseline: surface velocity (E-W, N-S), slope
- Exp S1: velocity magnitude, slope
- Exp S2: velocity (E-W, N-S)
- Exp S3: slope
- Exp S4: velocity (E-W, N-S), slope, hypsometry
- Exp S5: architecture complexity (e.g. without classification branch)

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Loss evolution

Baseline model: green, blue. Top: without slope. Bottom: without velocity.

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Results

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Results

Lopez-Uroz et al. 2024, Using deep learning for glacier thickness estimation at a regional scale.

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Integration of expert's knowledge

Expert's knowledge: ice thickness maximum at the balance line (z_{50})
 → hypsometry (altitude - area distribution)

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Integration of expert's knowledge

A) average without hypsometry B) standard deviation without hypsometry
C) average with hypsometry D) standard deviation with hypsometry

Lopez-Uroz et al. 2024, Using deep learning for glacier thickness estimation at a regional scale.

Conclusions

- SAR images constitutes one of the most important sources for Earth observation.
- InSAR provides surface displacement measurements over large area and of high accuracy.
- The development of AI based approaches for SAR image processing presents both challenges and opportunities.

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Objectives

- What is Unmixing? Why Unmixing?
- What is linear Unmixing?
- Pure pixel and No Pure Pixel Scenarios
- Endmember Extraction
- What is Spectral Variability?
- Difference between Supervised unmixing, Semisupervised unmixing, and Blind Unmixing
- Geometrical Unmixing
- Least Square-based unmixing
- Autoencoders and CNNs for Unmixing
- Hands-on and exercises. We released an open-source Python-based collection of unmixing approaches called HySUPP.

Hyperspectral Databcube

- **Hyperspectral cameras:** provide contiguous electromagnetic spectra
- **The spectral signature:** allowing to distinguish between materials with different characteristics.

3

- Estimating the fractional abundances of the pure spectra of constituent materials (called Endmembers) within a pixel
- Subjective and depends on how endmembers are defined

4

Linear versus Nonlinear Unmixing

5

Linear Unmixing

6

Linear Mixture Model and Data Simplex

7

Pixel Quiz!

8

9

Taxonomy of Linear Unmixing Methods

10

SPECTRAL VARIABILITY

1. Atmospheric effects
2. Illumination variations (Terrain topography, occlusion of the light)
3. The intrinsic variation of materials

R. A. Bonosi et al., "Spectral Variability in Hyperspectral Data Unmixing: A comprehensive review," in IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine
 J. Theiler et al., "Spectral Variability of Remotely Sensed Target Materials: Causes, Models, and Strategies for Mitigation and Robust Exploitation," in IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine

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Pure Pixel and No Pure Pixel Assumption

12

Conventional Linear Models for Unmixing

13

Norm

- A function which maps a vector space to the nonnegative real numbers

- p-norm of vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$

$$\|\mathbf{x}\|_p := \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|^p \right)^{1/p}$$

- ℓ_1 :

$$\|\mathbf{x}\|_1 := \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|$$

- ℓ_2 :

$$\|\mathbf{x}\|_2 := \sqrt{x_1^2 + \dots + x_n^2}$$

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Supervised Unmixing

- Endmembers are known
 - Extracted using geometrical approaches
 - Selected from a Library
 - Measured in a LAB or the field

- Estimating A

$$(\hat{A}) = \arg \min_A \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda \phi(A) \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0$$

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Blind Unmixing

- Estimating E and A

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \phi_1(E) + \lambda_2 \phi_2(A) \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0, 0 \leq E \leq 1$$

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Sparse Unmixing (José M. Bioucas Dias)

- Only a few endmembers can reconstruct the mixed hyperspectral pixel

- Estimating X

$$(\hat{X}) = \arg \min_X \frac{1}{2} \|Y - DX\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^n \|x_{(i)}\|_q$$

Observed data: $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n}$
 Endmember: $D \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m}$
 Abundances: $X \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$
 Noise: $N \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n}$

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Unmixing Using Autoencoders

- Encoder encodes an input into abundances: $\mathbf{a} = \sigma(W_{en}(\mathbf{y}))$
- Decoder reconstruct the signal: $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \sigma(W_{de}(\mathbf{a}))$
- Endmembers: the weights of the decoders
- Often deep encoder, shallow decoder

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Realization of ASC and ANC

1. Applying Nonnegative activation function such as ReLU and Normalization for ASC

$$a = \frac{a}{\sum_{i=1}^r a_i}$$

2. Or

$$a = \frac{|a|}{\sum_{i=1}^r |a_i|}$$

3. Softmax

$$\text{Softmax}(a) = \frac{e^{a_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^r e^{a_i}}$$

4. Adding a penalty term to the loss function

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Common Loss Functions

- $L_{reg} = L(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) + \lambda J(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{W}_{de}, \mathbf{W}_{en})$

- L is often ℓ_2 norm (or MSE)

$$L_{\ell_2}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \|\mathbf{y} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2$$

- or SAD

$$L_{SAD}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \arccos\left(\frac{\mathbf{y}^T \hat{\mathbf{y}}}{\|\mathbf{y}\|_2 \|\hat{\mathbf{y}}\|_2}\right)$$

- The regularization term J could be a Minimum Volume Penalty

$$J = MV(E) = MV(\mathbf{W}_{de})$$

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Supervised Unmixing (Unmixing Chain)

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FCLSU: Fully Constrained Least Squares Unmixing

Endmember extraction (Often using geometrical approaches)

Then FCLSU

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{EA}\|_F^2 \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n, \mathbf{A} \geq \mathbf{0}$$

Or FCLSU + spatial regularizer ϕ (it could be TV, sparsity promoting penalty, or a combination of them)

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{EA}\|_F^2 + \lambda R(\mathbf{A}) \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n, \mathbf{A} \geq \mathbf{0}$$

D. Heinz, C.-J. Chang and M. L. G. Althouse, "Fully constrained least-squares based linear unmixing (hyperspectral image classification)," IEEE 1999 International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS'99) (Cat. No.99CH36923), 1999, pp. 1421-1423 vol.2, doi: 10.1109/IGARSS.1999.774644.

23

UnDIP: Hyperspectral Unmixing Using Deep Image Prior

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{EA}\|_F^2 + \lambda R(\mathbf{A}) \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n, \mathbf{A} \geq \mathbf{0}$$

$$(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{E}f_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\mathbf{Z})\|_F^2 \text{ st. } \hat{\mathbf{A}} = f_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\mathbf{Z})$$

B. Rafti, B. Kozicki, P. Scheunders and P. Ghamis, "UnDIP: Hyperspectral Unmixing Using Deep Image Prior," in IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 60, pp. 1-15, 2022, Art no. 5048116, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2021.3057920.

24

MVC-NMF: Minimum volume constrained nonnegative matrix factorization

MVC-NMF uses the square of the volume of the simplex defined by the columns of E .

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 V^2(E) \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0, E \geq 0$$

Where $E = [e_{(i)}]$ and

$$V(E) = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \left| \det \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & 1 \\ e_{(1)} & \dots & e_{(r)} \end{bmatrix} \right|$$

L. Miao and H. Qi, "Endmember Extraction From Highly Mixed Data Using Minimum Volume Constrained Nonnegative Matrix Factorization," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 765-777, March 2007, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2006.889466.

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CoNMF: Collaborative nonnegative matrix factorization for remotely sensed hyperspectral unmixing

Promoting sparsity on abundances and MV on the simplex

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|E - m\mathbf{1}_r^T\|_F^2 + \lambda_2 \sum_{i=1}^r \|a_{(i)}\|_2^q \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0, 0 < q \leq 1$$

Selecting the tuning parameter is challenging.

J. Li, J. M. Bioucas-Dias and A. Plaza, "Collaborative nonnegative matrix factorization for remotely sensed hyperspectral unmixing," 2012 *IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2012, pp. 3078-3081, doi: 10.1109/IGARSS.2012.6350775.

26

NMF-QMV: Nonnegative Matrix Factorization-Quadratic Minimum Volume

- Quadratic MV penalties and no spatial regularization

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda \|EB - O\|_F^2 \text{ st. } A \in \Theta_{r-1}^+, \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0$$

- Parameter selection

$$\lambda_{\text{opt}} = \arg \min_{\lambda} D(G, \hat{E}_{\lambda})$$

- $D \triangleq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \text{dist}(g_j, \hat{E}_{\lambda})$,

- $G \triangleq \{g_1, \dots, g_n\}$

(the set of vertices of the convex hull of the observations projected into a subspace)

QMV	Center	TV	Boundary
B	I_r	$I_r - \mathbf{1}_r \mathbf{1}_r^T / r$	I_r
O	$m\mathbf{1}_r^T$	O	Extremes

L. Zhuang, C.-H. Lin, M. A. T. Figueiredo and J. M. Bioucas-Dias, "Regularization Parameter Selection in Minimum Volume Hyperspectral Unmixing," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 9858-9877, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2019.2929776.

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Estimating in Subspace

The unmixing problem can be solved in a subspace

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|EB - O\|_F^2 \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0$$

Instead, we solve

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|V^T(Y - EA)\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|V^T(EB - O)\|_F^2 \text{ st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0$$

Where $V^T V = I_r$ and can be obtained by SVD or PCA.

Pros: Computationally efficient and more robust to noise

Cons: Estimating negative values for E

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EDAA: Entropic Descent Archetypal Analysis for Blind Hyperspectral Unmixing

- The archetypal analysis formulation was used to enforce the endmembers to be convex combinations of the pixels

$$(\hat{A}, \hat{B}) = \arg \min_{A, B} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - YBA\|_F^2 \text{ st. } a_{(i)} \in \Delta_r \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$b_{(j)} \in \Delta_n \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq r$$

- Where $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ and therefore the columns of $B = [b_1, \dots, b_r]$ belong to the simplex Δ_n .

- The problem is solved using an Entropic descent algorithm (EDA).

Alexandre Zouaoui, Gerleon Muhawenayo, Behnood Rasti, Jocelyn Chanussot, Julien Mairal, "Entropic Descent Archetypal Analysis for Blind Hyperspectral Unmixing," Submitted to *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*.

29

Tensor Models

Not interpretable

CPD: canonical polyadic decomposition

Tucker decomposition

Interpretable: rank- $(L_i, L_i, 1)$ decomposition for a 3rd-order tensor

$$\mathcal{Y} = \sum_{i=1}^r A_i \circ a_i = \sum_{i=1}^r K_i B_i^T \circ e_i + \mathcal{N}, K_i \geq 0, B_i \geq 0, e_i \geq 0$$

$$\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2 \times P}$$

$$A_i = K_i B_i^T: \text{Abundances } n_1 \times n_2 \text{ (rank } L_i)$$

$$K_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2}, B_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2 \times n_2} \text{ (rank } L_i)$$

$$n = n_1 \times n_2$$

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Matrix-Vector Nonnegative Tensor Factorization

MVNTF solves

$$(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \sum_{i=1}^r \mathbf{K}_i \mathbf{B}_i^T \odot \mathbf{e}_i\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|\sum_{i=1}^r \mathbf{K}_i \mathbf{B}_i^T - \mathbf{1}_{n_1} \mathbf{1}_{n_2}^T\|_F^2 \quad \text{s.t. } \mathbf{K} \geq 0, \mathbf{B} \geq 0, \mathbf{E} \geq 0$$

The Frobenius norm for a third-order tensor is given by

$$\mathcal{X} = \sqrt{\sum_i \sum_j \sum_k x_{ijk}^2}$$

- Other variations were proposed using TV and ℓ_1 on abundances.

Y. Qian, F. Xiong, S. Ding, S. Zhou, and Y. Y. Tang, "Matrix-vector nonnegative tensor factorization for blind unmixing of hyperspectral images," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 2023.

31

Sparse unmixing by variable splitting and augmented Lagrangian

SUnSAL:

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DA}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{a}_{(i)}\|_1 \quad \text{st. } \mathbf{1}_n^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n, \mathbf{A} \geq 0$$

SUnSAL-TV:

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DA}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{a}_{(i)}\|_1 + \lambda_2 TV(\mathbf{A}) \quad \text{st. } \mathbf{A} \geq 0$$

Using the nonisotropic TV

$$TV(\mathbf{A}) = \|\mathbf{RA}\|_1, \mathbf{RA} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}_h \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{D}_v \mathbf{A} \end{bmatrix}$$

J. M. Bruna-Dias and B. A. T. Figueiredo, "Robust sparse regression for nonnegative matrix factorization: Application to hyperspectral unmixing," *2012 2nd Workshop on Hyperspectral Image and Signal Processing: Evolution in Remote Sensing*, 2012, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/WHISPERS.2012.6564023.

M. G. Sordache, J. M. Bruna-Dias and A. Plaza, "Total Variation Sparsity Regularization for Sparse Hyperspectral Unmixing," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 4684-4692, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2012.2310190.

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Sparse unmixing by variable splitting and augmented Lagrangian

Collaborative sparse unmixing

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DA}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{j=1}^m \|\mathbf{a}_j\|_2 \quad \text{st. } \mathbf{A} \geq 0$$

M. G. Sordache, J. M. Bruna-Dias and A. Plaza, "Collaborative Sparse Regression for Hyperspectral Unmixing," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 341-354, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2013.2249201.

L. Ding, T. R. Meyer, J. Chen, A. L. Bertoni and C. J. Allen, "Hyperspectral Image Unmixing With Endmember Bundles and Group Sparsity Inducing Mixed Norms," in *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 28, no. 7, pp. 3433-3440, July 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIP.2019.2897254.

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SUnAA: Sparse Unmixing using Archetypal Analysis

- We assume that the endmembers of interest are a convex combination of the library endmembers

$$(\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DBA}\|_F^2 \quad \text{st. } \mathbf{1}_n^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n, \mathbf{A} \geq 0$$

$$\mathbf{1}_m^T \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{1}_n^T, \mathbf{B} \geq 0$$

- Where $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$ and therefore the columns of $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_r]$ belong to the simplex Δ_m .
- The problem is solved using an active set algorithm

Behrood Rasti, Alexandre Zouaoui, Julien Mairal, Jocelyn Chanussot, "SUnAA: Sparse Unmixing using Archetypal Analysis," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*.

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FASUN: FAST SEMI-SUPERVISED UNMIXING USING ALTERNATING DIRECTION METHOD OF MULTIPLIERS

We propose a mixing model for observed spectra in

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{DBA} + \mathbf{N}, \quad (1)$$

We want to solve

$$(\hat{\mathbf{B}}, \hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DBA}\|_F^2$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{B} \geq 0, \mathbf{1}_n^T \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{1}_n^T, \text{ and } \mathbf{A} \geq 0, \mathbf{1}_n^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n^T, \quad (4)$$

Where $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$ and therefore the columns of $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_r]$ belong to the simplex Δ_m .

Problem (4) is non-convex, we solve in two steps using cyclic descent

A-step: when \mathbf{B} is fixed and **B-step:** \mathbf{A} is fixed.

In every step, we are dealing with a convex optimization, and therefore, every solution of the steps successively decreases the loss function, which leads to a minimum.

The convergence of the final solution is guaranteed upon the convergence of every step throughout the iterations.

Behrood Rasti, "FASUN: FAST SEMI-SUPERVISED UNMIXING USING ALTERNATING DIRECTION METHOD OF MULTIPLIERS," *IEEE WHISPERS* 2023.

35

SUnS: Sparse Unmixing Using Soft-Shrinkage

Convex v.s. non-convex

Number of endmembers

ASC and ℓ_1

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{X}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DX}\|_F^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{X}\|_1$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{X} \geq 0, \mathbf{1}_n^T \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{1}_n^T,$$

$$(\hat{\mathbf{B}}, \hat{\mathbf{A}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{DBA}\|_F^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{B}\|_1$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{A} \geq 0, \mathbf{1}_n^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1}_n^T, 0 \leq \mathbf{B} \leq \mathbf{1}.$$

Behrood Rasti, Alexandre Zouaoui, Julien Mairal, Jocelyn Chanussot, "Fast Semi-supervised Unmixing using Non-convex Optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*.

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MiSiCNet: Minimum Simplex Convolutional Network for Deep Hyperspectral Unmixing

$$(\hat{E}, \hat{A}) = \arg \min_{E, A} \frac{1}{2} \|Y - EA\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|E - m\mathbf{1}_r^T\|_F^2 + \lambda_2 R(A)$$

$$\text{st. } \mathbf{1}_r^T A = \mathbf{1}_n, A \geq 0, 0 \leq E \leq 1$$

S. Razi, S. Kiroka, P. Scheunders and J. Chanussot, "MiSiCNet: Minimum Simplex Convolutional Network for Deep Hyperspectral Unmixing," in IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 60, pp. 1-15, 2022, Art. no. 5522815, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2022.3148904.

TABLE II
RMSE (SIMULATED 1). THE BEST PERFORMANCES ARE SHOWN IN BOLD.

	FCLSU	UnDIP	uDAS	CyCUNet	Collab.	NMF-QMV	MiSiCNet
20dB	11.13±1.93	8.75±0.56	9.40±1.73	17.97±2.93	10.69±1.53	3.81±0.20	3.90±0.08
30dB	12.28±3.44	7.19±0.87	9.40±1.91	17.83±4.73	11.22±2.29	1.81±0.42	1.80±0.04
40dB	12.29±2.49	7.73±0.87	9.36±2.03	17.97±7.02	10.07±1.68	1.70±0.90	1.23±0.05
50dB	11.15±2.72	7.36±0.88	8.46±2.04	16.07±0.76	10.35±2.02	3.71±0.74	1.21±0.08

TABLE III
RMSE (SIMULATED 2). THE BEST PERFORMANCES ARE SHOWN IN BOLD.

	FCLSU	UnDIP	uDAS	CyCUNet	Collab.	NMF-QMV	MiSiCNet
20dB	12.55±1.89	12.15±1.04	11.43±2.69	19.51±5.89	12.05±0.61	4.03±0.54	3.96±0.04
30dB	21.45±2.49	10.49±0.21	12.57±5.11	15.87±2.71	13.83±1.94	3.79±2.33	2.45±0.02
40dB	21.62±1.11	10.52±0.22	10.94±4.29	14.57±1.3	14.11±1.93	3.73±1.13	2.15±0.03
50dB	22.89±2.71	10.37±0.17	10.76±4.24	15.96±2.02	14.14±1.18	6.91±1.17	2.12±0.03

Experimental Results

Experimental Results

Experimental Results

RMSE (SAMSON DATASET). THE BEST PERFORMANCES ARE SHOWN IN BOLD.

	FCLSU	UnDIP	uDAS	CyCUNet	Collab.	NMF-QMV	MiSiCNet
Soil	17.66	17.78	17.99	24.17	15.06	52.35	2.76
Tree	6.53	13.30	13.83	13.86	6.07	39.90	2.44
Water	14.92	20.96	23.03	26.54	11.81	45.98	2.07
Overall	13.87	17.63	18.67	22.21	11.59	46.36	2.44

HySUPP: HyperSpectral Unmixing Python Package

HySUPP Unique Features

- ✓ Open Source
- ✓ Completeness
- ✓ Reproducibility
- ✓ Extensibility
- ✓ Benchmarking

- A command line instruction for running
`$ python unmixing.py mode=semi data=DC1 model=SU CNN noise.SNR=30`
- Easy to apply parameter tuning
`$ python unmixing.py mode=semi data=DC1 model=SU CNN projection=True model.niters=8000 model.noisy_input=False noise.SNR=30`

Benedict Razi, Alexandre Chaux, Julien Mairal, and Jocelyn Chanussot, "Image Processing and Machine Learning for Hyperspectral Imaging: An Overview and the HySUPP Python Package," IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing.

Experimental Results (HySUPP)

SPECIFICATIONS OF THE SYNTHETIC DATASETS USED IN THE EXPERIMENTS.

	# endmembers (r)	# atoms in D (m)	# pixels (n)	Main features
DC1	5	240	5625 (75 × 75)	Pure pixels
DC2	9	240	10000 (100 × 100)	Pure pixels, Spectral variability
DC3	6	498	11025 (105 × 105)	No pure pixels, 2 points on the data simplex facets

Experimental Results (HySUPP)

Further Study and References

- Hyperspectral Unmixing Overview (main references for this course)
 - Behrooz Rasti, Alexandre Zissou, Julien Malat, and Jocelyn Chanussot, "Image Processing and Machine Learning for Hyperspectral Unmixing: An Overview and the HySUPP Python Package", IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing.
 - J. M. Bioucas-Dias, A. Plaza, N. Dobigeon, M. Parente, Q. Du, P. Gader, and J. Chanussot, "Hyperspectral unmixing overview: Geometrical, statistical, and sparse regression-based approaches," IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 354-370, April 2012.
- Estimation of number of endmembers (Subspace Identification)
 - J. M. Bioucas-Dias and J. M. P. Nascimento, "Hyperspectral Subspace Identification," in IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 46, no. 8, pp. 2435-2445, Aug. 2008, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2008.918089.
 - B. Stolt, M. O. Ulfarsson and J. R. Sveinsson, "Hyperspectral Subspace Identification Using SURF," in IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 2481-2485, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2015.2485999.
 - Chenxi Chang and Qian Du, "Estimation of number of spectrally distinct signal sources in hyperspectral imagery," in IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 608-619, March 2004, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2003.839185.
 - A. Ambikapathi, T.-H. Chan, C.-Y. Chi and K. Keiser, "Hyperspectral Data Geometry Based Estimation of Number of Endmembers Using p-Norm Based Pure Pixel Identification Algorithm," in IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 51, no. 5, pp. 2793-2799, May 2013, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2012.2213261.
- Spectral Variability, endmember variabilities
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 - J. Theiler et al., "Spectral Variability of Remotely Sensed Target Materials: Causes, Models, and Strategies for Mitigation and Robust Exploitation," in IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine.
- Nonlinear Unmixing
 - R. Heylen, M. Parente and P. Gader, "A Review of Nonlinear Hyperspectral Unmixing Methods," in IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 1844-1848, June 2014, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2014.2320576.
 - B. Rasti, B. Kojala and P. Scheunders, "HapkeCNN: Blind Nonlinear Unmixing for Isotonic Mixtures Using Hapke Model and Convolutional Neural Network," in IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 60, pp. 1-15, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2022.3202490.
- Comparison of Autoencoders for Blind Unmixing
 - B. Rastou, J. R. Sveinsson and M. O. Ulfarsson, "Blind Hyperspectral Unmixing Using Autoencoders: A Critical Comparison," in IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing, vol. 15, pp. 1340-1372, 2022, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2021.3140154.

Hands-on Exercises

Check out the GitHub repository <https://github.com/BehroozRasti/HySUPP>

If you don't have a GPU, then you can sign up for a Google account so you can work with google Colab and work with my IEEE IADF Unmixing Tutorial. There is a recorded lecture including hands-on exercises. Check out the GitHub repository https://github.com/BehroozRasti/Unmixing_Tutorial_IEEE_IADF

Then follow the instructions on the GitHub page and install the dependencies.

Appreciation

A fractal texture model for multi-spectral images

Prof. Mihai Ivanovici
Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania

1

Why do we need a model?

2

Outline

- Fractals – a brief introduction
- Fractal models – how to generate?
- Fractal analysis
- A color fractal image model (in RGB)
- 1, 2, 3... infinity (i.e. HSI)

3

What is a Fractal?

- A set with similar properties along multiple scales
 - Self-similarity (as we zoom in, the object geometric or probabilistic properties are the same)
- A fractal is, by definition, a set for which the Hausdorff Besicovitch dimension strictly exceeds the topological dimension

4

Examples of Fractal Sets

Sierpinski triangle and pyramid

Sierpinski carpet and Menger sponge

5

Fractal Geometry

- Benoît Mandelbrot 1983
 - In order to describe self-similar sets (called fractals)
- Euclidian geometry – unable to describe the shape of a cloud, a mountain, a coastline or a tree
- The main fractal tools: *fractal dimension* and *lacunarity*

6

Motivation

- Fractals are everywhere in nature
 - Math is everywhere, signals are everywhere...

7

Deterministic Fractal Generation

- Recursive / iterative technique from an initial shape

8

Fractal Generation Techniques

- Probabilistic approaches (fractional Brownian motion, midpoint displacement algorithm etc.)
- Spectral approaches (FFT-based)
- Other approaches (e.g. Takagi, random cuts)
- All allow only for generation of black-and-white or grey-scale images

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Fractional Brownian Motion

- **fBm** (a.k.a. $1/f^2$ noise) is the most useful mathematical model for random fractals
- For a fBm $V_H(t)$ $H = Hurst\ factor$

$$\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$$

$$\Delta V = V(t_2) - V(t_1)$$

$$E\{|\Delta V|\} \propto |\Delta t|^H$$

$$E\{|\Delta V|^2\} \propto |\Delta t|^{2H}$$

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Midpoint Displacement 1D

Recursive construction after initialisation (RED points)

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Midpoint Displacement 2D

Recursive construction after initialisation (RED points)

Different complexity "clouds"

Extension to Color

- Independent (uncorrelated) color planes
- First approach: an RGB generator
 - Cubical shape space
- Modified Midpoint Displacement Algorithm for 5D spaces (objects)
 - 5D = x, y (space) + r, g, b (color)
- RGB Color Space used for generation
 - Equivalent to a band-selection visualization of HSI

Results using RGB color space

Fractal Generation Validation

- How to validate the generator without a color fractal estimator?
- Solution: complexity of the FBM αH
 - Mathematical proof
 - 3D histograms
 - Co-occurrence matrices (on each color plane)
 - 3D increments histograms

Mathematical Proof

$$\overline{|X(t_1, t_2) - X(s_1, s_2)|^2} \propto \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (t_i - s_i)^2 \right)^H$$

$$\sigma_i^2 = \left(\sqrt{\sum_{k=r,g,b} (X_k(t_1, t_2) - X_k(s_1, s_2))^2} \right)^2$$

M. Ivanovici and N. Richard, "Fractal Dimension of Color Fractal Images," in *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 227-235, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TIP.2010.2059032.

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Proof (cont.)

$$= \overline{[X_r(t_1, t_2) - X_r(s_1, s_2)]^2 + [X_g(t_1, t_2) - X_g(s_1, s_2)]^2 + [X_b(t_1, t_2) - X_b(s_1, s_2)]^2} =$$

$$= \overline{[X_r(t_1, t_2) - X_r(s_1, s_2)]^2} + \overline{[X_g(t_1, t_2) - X_g(s_1, s_2)]^2} + \overline{[X_b(t_1, t_2) - X_b(s_1, s_2)]^2} \propto$$

$$\propto 3 \cdot \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (t_i - s_i)^2 \right)^H \propto \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (t_i - s_i)^2 \right)^H$$

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3D histograms

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3D histograms analysis

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Forest top-like texture generation

□ based on a bidimensional Takagi color fractal

An application – forest segmentation

□ Template matching-based approach

Conclusions

- ❑ The fractal models are useful for the analysis of various real/natural objects, shapes, textures... in remote sensing and Earth Observation:
 - coastlines
 - river structures
 - forest
 - agricultural crops
 - ice and snow
 - clouds
 - ...

Further reading

M. Ivanovici and N. Richard, "Fractal Dimension of Color Fractal Images", in *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 227-235, Jan. 2011, DOI: 10.1109/TIP.2010.2059032

M. Ivanovici, "Fractal Dimension of Color Fractal Images with Correlated Color Component", in *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 29, pp. 8069 - 8082, Jul. 2020, DOI:10.1109/TIP.2020.3011283

R.M. Coliban, A. Radoi, M. Ivanovici, "A color and multispectral fractal model for forest region identification in satellite images", in *2016 International Conference on Communications (COMM)*, 9-10 Jun. 2016, DOI:10.1109/ICComm.2016.7528263

M. Ivanovici, A Multi-Spectral Fractal Image Model and Its Associated Fractal Dimension Estimator. *Fractal and Fractional*. 2023; 7(3):238. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fractalfract7030238>

FRACTAL ANALYSIS

- ❑ A multi-scale type of analysis
 - Fractal Measures (e.g. fractal dimension and lacunarity) for quantifying the complexity of a fractal object or signal / image with fractal properties (self-similarity)
- ❑ Applications
 - Image / texture characterization and classification
 - Image segmentation

Fractal dimension (FD)

- ❑ Captures the complexity of a fractal object
- ❑ Shows how much space is occupied by the fractal

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Fractal Dimension

- ❑ Can be computed for deterministic fractals, but only estimated for random fractals
- ❑ Comprised between E and $E+1$ (topological / Euclidian dimension) for binary and grey-scale fractal images

The Similarity Dimension

- ❑ 1-D N parts, scaled by ratio $r = 1/N \rightarrow Nr^1 = 1$

- ❑ 2-D N parts, scaled by ratio $r = 1/N^{1/2} \rightarrow Nr^2 = 1$

- ❑ 3-D N parts, scaled by ratio $r = 1/N^{1/3} \rightarrow Nr^3 = 1$

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Generalization

- For an object of N parts, each scaled down by a ratio r from the whole

$$Nr^D = 1$$

- Therefore, the fractal (similarity) dimension D

$$D = \frac{\log N}{\log 1/r}$$

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Example – Sierpinski triangle

$$N = 3$$

$$r = 2$$

$$D = \frac{\log 3}{\log 2} = 1.585$$

The Hausdorff Dimension

The Hausdorff dimension $H^S(F)$ of a set F is the limit when δ (the diameter of the cover set) goes to zero:

$$H^S(F) = \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} H_\delta^S(F) \quad H_\delta^S(F) = \inf \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |U_i|^S \right\}$$

$\{U_i\}$ is the δ -cover of F , i.e. a countable (or finite) collection of sets of diameter at most δ that cover the set F

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The Box-Counting Dimension

- Let $N_\delta(F)$ be the smallest number of sets of diameter at most δ that can cover the set F .

- The *lower* and *upper box-counting dimensions* of F , which are the infimum and supremum limits of the set, are defined as follows:

$$\underline{\dim}_B F = \liminf_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log N_\delta(F)}{-\log \delta} \quad \overline{\dim}_B F = \limsup_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log N_\delta(F)}{-\log \delta}$$

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Box-Counting Dimension (2)

- If these two dimensions are equal then we refer to this value as the *box-counting dimension* or *box dimension* of F .

$$\dim_B F = \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log N_\delta(F)}{-\log \delta}$$

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Fractal Dimension Estimation

- Box-counting
 - Probabilistic box counting
 - Differential box counting
 - ...
- δ -parallel body (a.k.a. covering blanket, Minkowski sausage or morphological covers)
- PDS-based (Power Density Spectrum)

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The Box-Counting FD

- For different box-sizes (δ), count how many boxes ($N(\delta)$) are needed to cover the object / signal

$\delta_1 = 3$

$\delta_2 = 5$

$\delta_3 = 7$

$\delta_1 = 3$
 $N(\delta_1) = 48$

$\delta_2 = 5$
 $N(\delta_2) = 19$

$\delta_3 = 7$
 $N(\delta_3) = 8$

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The Box-Counting FD (II)

FD = the slope of the regression line through the points $\langle \log(\delta), -\log(N(\delta)) \rangle$

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The Voss Algorithm

- $P(m, \delta)$ – the probability of having m points inside a box of size δ
- The total number of boxes needed to cover the object/image is:

$$\langle N(\delta) \rangle = \sum_{m=1}^N \frac{M}{m} P(m, \delta) = M \sum_{m=1}^N \frac{1}{m} P(m, \delta)$$

- $N(\delta)$ is proportional to δ^{-FD}

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Our color RGB approach

- A colour extension of the Voss probabilistic (box-counting like) approach

- We consider the colour image a 5D object (pixel's spatial coordinates + color)

- We use hyper-cubes (5D boxes) in the (x, y, R, G, B) space

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Results on Color Fractal Images

2.237

3.258

3.840

The Colour FD should be comprised between 2 and 5

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Results on natural fractal images

2.0

3.39

3.71

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Improvements

- Small boxes are affected by quantization noise / errors

Max err = ± 0.5

$$\varepsilon_{\max}(\delta) = \frac{0.5\delta^2}{\delta^3}$$

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Improvements (2)

- Solution: weight the importance of the boxes for the computation of the regression line

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Extension to more bands

- Consider the correlation between spectral bands?

- Yes – more complex model, but more realistic
 - Model the correlation between bands in the generation process
 - RGB channels are usually highly correlated
 - Multi-spectral acquisition sensors have correlated spectral bands
- No – simpler model, but not too realistic
 - Independent bands generated independently

M. Ivanovici, "Fractal Dimension of Color Fractal Images With Correlated Color Components," in *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 29, pp. 8069-8082, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TIP.2020.3011283.

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Model the band correlation

The probability density of a multi-variate normal distribution is:

$$w(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{k/2} |\Sigma|^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}-\mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{x}-\mu)}$$

- ▶ $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)$ is the vector data format
- ▶ $k = \text{rank}(\Sigma)$ is the size of the vector space (3 for RGB)
- ▶ $|\Sigma|$ is the determinant of the covariance matrix
- ▶ $\mu = (\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_k)$ is the mean vector of the color set

The covariance matrix has the following shape:

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \sigma_{rg} & \sigma_{rb} \\ \sigma_{rg} & 1 & \sigma_{gb} \\ \sigma_{rb} & \sigma_{gb} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

where $\sigma_{\xi\eta}$ is the centered moment of the pair (ξ, η) , i.e. a measure of the correlation between the two variables $(\xi, \eta = r, g, b)$.

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Color fractal images with correlated color

(a) $\sigma_{rg} = 0.9, \sigma_{rb} = 0.1$ (b) $\sigma_{rg} = 0.5, \sigma_{rb} = 0.1$ (c) $\sigma_{rg} = 0.1, \sigma_{gb} = 0.9, \sigma_{rb} = 0.1$ $\sigma_{gb} = 0.5, \sigma_{rb} = 0.9$

Figure 1: Color fractal images of the same complexity ($H=0.9$), but different color content due to correlation between channels.

- ▶ for low complexity (i.e. small fractal dimension and small variation of increments), complex color content results
- ▶ more difficult to prove the validity of the fractal model...

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2 correlated channels (red and green)

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Validity of the model

$$\sigma_i^2 = \left\{ \sqrt{\sum_{k=r,g} [X_k(t_1, t_2) - X_k(s_1, s_2)]^2} \right\}^2$$

$$\sigma_i^2 = \frac{[X_r(t_1, t_2) - X_r(s_1, s_2)]^2 + [X_g(t_1, t_2) - X_g(s_1, s_2)]^2 + \dots}{\dots + 2[X_r(t_1, t_2) - X_r(s_1, s_2)][X_g(t_1, t_2) - X_g(s_1, s_2)]}$$

$$\sigma_i^2 = \frac{[X_r(t_1, t_2) - X_r(s_1, s_2)]^2 + [X_g(t_1, t_2) - X_g(s_1, s_2)]^2}{+ 2[X_r(t_1, t_2) - X_r(s_1, s_2)][X_g(t_1, t_2) - X_g(s_1, s_2)]}$$

$$\sigma_i^2 \propto 2(1 + \sigma_{rg}) \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (t_i - s_i)^2 \right)^H \propto \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (t_i - s_i)^2 \right)^H \quad \square$$

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Preliminary conclusions

- Mathematical proof of fractal model validity for color images with 2 correlated components
 - Also for 3 or N color components → this allows the extension to multi- and hyper-spectral domains
- Two parameters to control the resulting images
 - H – for the surface complexity (texture roughness)
 - Σ – for the correlation between channels (color content complexity)
- Global normalization is required for metrological purposes

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Extension to multi-spectral

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The multi-spectral fractal image data cubes

(a) Low complexity MSFI (b) Mid complexity MSFI (c) High complexity MSFI

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Visualization of multi-spectral images

- Performed using the band selection (left), linear model (middle) and non-linear (ANN) (right) models previously presented by Radu Coliban

(a) BS RGB

(b) Lin RGB

(c) ANN RGB

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Analysis box adaptation

Parallel covers for a pixel

MS FD estimation on a known image

EO Applications of fractal analysis

- ❑ *How long is the coast of Britain?*
- ❑ Fractal analysis of river networks based on remote sensing data
- ❑ Land cover analysis (classification, change detection)
- ❑ Quantifying urban patterns
- ❑ Digital Elevation Models based on fractal shapes

Instead of conclusions

- ❑ The fractal model is valid for multi-spectral images
 - with small number of wavelengths/bands
- ❑ Do the generated vectors correspond to real spectral signatures of real/natural materials?
 - How to validate the model?
 - Quantify the loss of information when converting to RGB color images
- ❑ What if we increase the spectral resolution?

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UAV data processing: from images to measures
Operational ISSUES

1. CROP SYSTEMS CLASSIFICATION (crop + soil) → CAP controls
2. ZONATION → at landscape level CLUSTER ANALYSIS
3. MANAGEMENT OF VARIABLE RATE APPROACHES → PRESCRIPTION MAPS
4. MAPPING SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF AGRONOMIC PARAMETERS (e.g. N, Organic Carbon, water potential, Evapotranspiration etc.)

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- WHICH SPECTRAL DISCRIMINANTS ?
- SPECTRAL SIGNATURE AT THE SINGLE TIME (along the growing season of crop)
 - TEMPORAL PROFILE OF SPECTRAL INDEX (VI)
 - Yearly VI temporal profile
 - Phenological metrics
 - GEOMETRIC FEATURES OF CROPS DERIVED FROM CANOPY HEIGHT MODELS (digital photogrammetry/LiDAR)

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→ PIXEL-BASED CLASSIFIERS ARE PREFERABLE. AN OBJECT-BASED approach could limit the detection of some important effects of local variability of crops/soil

Joint classification

Prescription maps can be also considered as intra-plot zonation, making possible to map those areas having different agronomic behaviour within a single field.

working at landscape level, zonation can be used to map average FIELD behaviour making possible to calibrate deductions for a proper management by Consortia or big farm companies. This is typical, for example, when looking for atmospheric adversities effects (drought, hail, storms, etc) or when deciding the time of harvest at field level.

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1. PRESCRIPTION MAPS: spectral index maps can be thresholded or clustered to derive PRESCRIPTION MAPS to be interpreted by variable rate machineries to distribute agronomic treatments with different intensity

2. ESTIMATION MAPS: Ground measures at a single or multiple times are compared with Spectral Index local values to calibrate regressive models useful for generating estimates of biophysical parameters

SPECTRAL INDICES
MAIN APPLICATIONS IN PRECISION FARMING

A) Zoning is made at field level
 B) One image at the right time along the growing season of crop can be enough to derive a useful PM.
 C) Relative spectral index differences are more important than absolute values → a simplified (qualitative and relative) remote sensing is enough to generate reliable results.

1. PRESCRIPTION MAPS (PM)

Multispectral image → Spectral index map (es. NDVI) → ZONES → Interpretation of ZONES → PRESCRIPTION MAPS

Es. $NDVI = \frac{NIR - R}{NIR + Red}$

Variable rate machineries for PA

Spectrum of crop

SPECTRAL INDICES
MAIN APPLICATIONS IN PRECISION FARMING

When working with very high resolution imagery (e.g. DRONES) some further steps have to be done, especially when working with crops like orchards or vineyards where monitored crop is not continuous

NDVI MAP → Automatic identification of vegetated pixels (vines) → Spatial interpolation to recover spatial continuity of representation → GEOSTATISTICS

SPECTRAL INDICES
REMAINING CRITICALITIES

- WHICH IS THE "BEST" SPECTRAL INDEX?**
 Most limiting factor is the spectral resolution of available sensors
- WHICH CRITERION has to be adopted to translate VIGOUR MAPS into the correspondent PRESCRIPTION MAPS?**
 Different criteria generate different prescription maps → different intensity of treatments over crops.
- WHICH MINIMUM MAPPING UNIT (MMU)?**
 Machineries performances and architecture play an important role to define this parameter → very high resolution imagery from sensors is really important?
- HOW MANY CLASSES OF INTENSITY OF TREATEMENTS MUST BE MAPPED IN PRESCRIPTION MAPS? VALUE OF THRESHOLDS?**
- WHICH IS THE BEST TIME ALONG THE GROWING SEASON OF CROPS TO OPERATE THE ACQUISITION? ONE OR MORE ACQUISITIONS?**

SPECTRAL INDICES
TIME OF THE ANALYSIS

WHICH IS THE BEST TIME ALONG THE GROWING SEASON OF CROPS TO OPERATE THE ACQUISITION?
 An example on vineyard

NDVI values: 0.20 (red), 0.70 (green)

SPECTRAL INDICES
SCALE OF ZONATION

Aerial dataset (GSD = 1 m) vs. Satellite dataset (GSD = 30 m)

June 2013, Sept 2013, June 2014, Sept 2014

SPECTRAL INDICES
NUMBER OF CLUSTERS

HOW MANY CLASSES?

NDVI map → 3 vigour classes → 5 vigour classes → 5 vigour classes

MINIMUM MAPPING UNIT (MMU)?

Prescription maps can be obtained by ZONING maps of opportune spectral indices (NDVI, NDRE, etc.) or, directly, maps of ESTIMATES of agronomic parameters obtained by REGRESSION or ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-based systems relating them to spectral measures.

ZONING can be achieved

- a) MANUALLY/INTERACTIVELY, possibly interpreting the HISTOGRAM of the map to be ZONED
- b) AUTOMATICALLY by CLUSTER ANALYSIS

When working with satellite data, to refine spatial patterns, it is possible to oversample the data. A better result can be achieved by preventively FILTERING (low pass) the map and then (over-)RESAMPLE it.

FILTERING: low pass FILTERING is useful to reduce local variability. High pass FILTERING is useful to emphasize radiometric borders. OUTPUT image preserve the same GSD as INPUT one

RESAMPLING: to virtually reduce GSD one can OVERSAMPLE. To virtually enlarge GSD one can DOWNSAMPLE.

MANUAL/INTERACTIVE ZONING

The user analyzes, perceptively, the IMAGE HISTOGRAM of the spectral index/parameters and proceed to define thresholds where significant breaks can be recognized

ZONING by SPATIAL CLUSTERING

Ordinary UNSUPERVISED CLASSIFICATION algorithms (e.g. K-means) can be used to ZONE the field operating on a single band (NDVI, NDRE, etc.) or on multiple bands (NDVI+NDRE+NDWI etc.) or directly on native bands of the multispectral image.

ZONING by SPATIAL CLUSTERING

Different spectral indices can be also jointly used and processed by UNSUPERVISED CLASSIFICATION to generate ZONES averagely similar in terms of indices values.

Vectorization (grid to vector)

INTERPRETING CLUSTERS

Once ZONES have been defined they have to be AGRONOMICALLY INTERPRETED.

A good starting point for INTERPRETATION is compute ZONAL STATISTICS for ZONES by ordinary GIS tools. STATISTICS may involve the starting NDVI map or, better other maps eventually available (other indices or bands or pedological infos...). ZONAL STATISTICS require that a vectorization of the ZONE MAP is achieved.

The translation of cluster spectral meaning into the correspondent agronomic information (intensity of differentiated treatment) needs a high level of knowledge from agronomists about the field the map is intended for. The expected solution relies on "transfer functions" (field dependent) relating the VI value to the rate. This has to be developed comparing ground and spectral measures for years (difficult).

Alternatively, agronomists can try to operate relatively, by comparing the average values of cluster VI and translating the VI percentage difference into a difference of treatment. The "medium" cluster can be the one that the ordinary amount of treatment is assigned. The others can be derived using the previously computed differences.

		Moscato Reale	
		Class limit	μ NDVI
Classi	High	Low (<=5% perc.)	0.513
	Medium	Medium (5%-75% perc.)	0.570
	Low	High (> 75% perc.)	0.572
		VD _{Low(HIGH)}	-0.21%
		VD _{High(HIGH)}	+7.26%

$$VD = \left(\frac{\mu_{L/H} - \mu_M}{\mu_M} \right) \cdot 100$$

where $\mu_{L/H}$: «Low» and «High» cluster VI mean value
 μ_M : «Medium» cluster VI mean value.

Multi-temporal NDVI maps

Multi-temporal DSM maps

Nel caso studio CHM= DSM-DTM (Regione Piemonte ICE 5m, $\sigma_z = 0.33$ m)

ESTIMATING AGRONOMIC PARAMETERS
Inferential approach

Ground measures at a single, or multiple times, are compared with Spectral Index local values to calibrate REGRESSIVE MODELS useful for generating estimates of biophysical parameters. This step can precede the one aimed at generating Prescription Maps, to make more immediate map interpretation. In fact, a farmer is more familiar with agronomic parameter values than spectra index ranges.

Heatmap for the correlation between vegetation indices and agronomic traits under different growth stages. J, Jointing stage; B, Booting stage; H, Heading stage; LF, Late flowering stage; IGF, Initial grain-filling stage; LGF, Late grain-filling stage; NS, not significant; *; p < 0.05; **; p < 0.01 (Jia, J., Zhu, Y., Tao, X., Chen, X., & Li, X. (2022). Rapid prediction of winter wheat yield and nitrogen use efficiency using consumer-grade unmanned aerial vehicles multispectral imagery. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13).

UAV data processing: from images to measures Photogrammetric ISSUES

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DISAFA - University of Torino

Image-based Survey Techniques

DIGITAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY

It aims at MEASURING objects by exploiting perspective properties of IMAGES. The basic idea is to translate in the image space ordinary techniques of topographic survey (e.g. forward intersection)

REMOTE SENSING

It aims at QUALIFYING objects (describing/measuring some chemical/physical features) exploiting their reflecting or emitting properties with respect to electro-magnetic radiation.

Both the techniques can be applied to whatever object. In agro-forestry applications, measured/qualified objects are generally those that can be observed from above (territorial application)

PHOTOGRAMMETRIC WORKFLOW

OPERATIONAL STEPS

- ⇒ Flight Planning
- ⇒ Image Acquisition
- ⇒ Ground Control Points Surveying
- ⇒ Image Block Bundle Adjustment (image resection)
- ⇒ Photogrammetric Restitution (measurements) → point cloud generation
- ⇒ Point cloud processing
- ⇒ Map/DSM production
- ⇒ Orthomosaic generation

IMAGE ACQUISITION

From ground to Image → upward equations

From Image to Ground → Downward equations (Restitution)

Flight plan is a fundamental step aimed at defining flight conditions with respect to:

- Available airplane/UAV
- Available camera/sensor
- Required accuracy for measures
- Required GSD (geometric resolution) of images

OUTPUTS of FLIGHT PLANNING:

- Relative Height of flight (AGL - above ground level)
- Flight direction (strips)
- Airplane/UAV speed
- Frequency of image acquisition
- Number of images to be acquired
- Number of Gigabytes required to store all images

FORWARD OVERLAP

(between adjacent images belonging to the same flight line - strip)

SIDE OVERLAP (between adjacent strips)

Stereoscopy conditions (the same point is imaged over 2 or more images) are satisfied only here

The image plane (p) is the place where scene is imaged by detectors. Focal length (f) is the distance between focal plane and focal point (PF) of the lens system (perspective centre).

The ratio $s = \frac{H}{f}$ defines the IMAGE SCALE and, consequently, the size of the whole scene (SWATH) and the GSD, once both physical pixel size (p) and CCD sensor size (p x s) are known.

Sensor	p (μm)	SWATH (km)	H (km)	f (mm)
MAIA (RPAS)	3.75	Variable	0 - 150	7.5
MAPIR (RPAS)	1.34	Variable	0 - 150	3.97

a) NEEDED INFOS: SENSOR TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Focal length (f)
- Physical pixel size (μ) [$2 \div 15 \mu\text{m}$]
- Physical sensor size (matrix of pixels). Can be known as N_r rows x N_c columns or $\text{mm H} \times \text{mm V}$ ($H \times V$).
- Minimum time lap between two consequent camera shots (seconds). Typical values range from 1 to 4 seconds.

b) FLIGHT PARAMETERS TO BE DECIDED (based on experience, area features, software performances)

- FORWARD overlap (R_{for}). Aerial photogrammetry (60-80 %); UAV photogr. (70-90%)
- SIDE overlap (R_{side}). Aerial photogrammetry (20-40 %); UAV photogr. (50-70%)
- UAV/airplane speed (v , to be compared with the minimum image time lap).
- Rotating wing UAV [0-18 km/h]; Fixed wing UAV [40-70 km/h]; Airplane [200-500 km/h]
- camera ORIENTATION on BOARD on platform (rectangular sensor size)

FLIGHT PLANNING

1. The starting point is the REQUIRED PRECISION of the survey, that depends on the NOMINAL SCALE of the MAP the survey has to generate. 2 possible situations are given:

A case. Aerial photogrammetry (suitable for maps having a scale up to 1:1000) → Table of correspondence relating IMAGE SCALE and MAP NOMINAL SCALE.

Once suitable image scale is known (λ), AGL height (H_{AGL}) can be computed as $H_{\text{AGL}} = \lambda \cdot f$ where f is the camera focal length

Map Nominal Scale	Image Scale
1:25000	1:25000
1:10000	1:20000
1:5000	1:15000
1:2000	1:8000
1:1000	1:5000

Alternatively a formula relating IMAGE SCALE (IS) and MAP NOMINAL SCALE (MS) can be used

$$IS = a \cdot \ln(MS) + b$$

where $a = 6467.6$ and $b = -40197$

B case: RPAS and close range photogrammetry (suitable for maps having a scale higher than 1:1000, e.g. 1:200) → once the required nominal scale of the map has been decided the correspondent precision is derived using the previously mentioned formula $PREC = 0.2 \times MS$. An empirical rule relating flight height (AGL) and expected precision (σ) is used to derive AGL height.

$$\sigma = 10^{-3} \times H_{\text{AGL}}$$

Map precision σ (m)	Map Nominal Scale
0.1	1:500
0.04	1:200
0.02	1:100
0.01	1:50

FLIGHT PLANNING

GSD (ground pixel size) of images has to be preventively decided

1. Image scale (s) can be computed comparing GSD with the physical pixel size (p): $s = GSD/p$
2. Consequently, the flying height (H) can be computed as: $H = s \times f$
3. The ground footprint of image ($H_f \times V_f$) can be therefore obtained as: $H_f = s \times H$, $V_f = s \times V$
4. Stereo Baseline (B) computation (distance between to consequent focal points)

$$B = H_f(1 - R_{\text{Lon}})$$

if flying with the horizontal size of image (H_f) parallel to the flying direction.

$$B = V_f(1 - R_{\text{Lon}})$$

if flying with the vertical size of image (V_f) parallel to the flying direction.

5. Image shots time lag (t_s) depends on baseline and UAV speed

$$t_s = B \cdot v [s]$$

The obtained value must be necessarily higher than the MINIMUM time lag that the sensor can operate with. If not, UAV speed must be reduced.

Approximate Cost: 13000 €
@December 2018

Technical Specifications

Image resolution	12 Megapixel (1280x960)	Shutter Type	Global Shutter
Focal Length	7.5 mm	Minimum Time Lap	n.d.
HFOV	35°	Bands	9 bands between 400 - 900 nm according to WV2 or S2 (see later)
Sensor Filter	RGB Bayer	Radiometric Resolution	8 bit, 10 bit, 12 bit
Pixel Physical Size	3.75 μm	Output Format	RAW
Weight	420 g		

FLIGHT PLANNING

6. Strip distance (I) can be computed

$$I = V_f(1 - R_{\text{Lat}})$$

if flying with the horizontal side of image (H_f) parallel to the flying direction.

$$I = H_f(1 - R_{\text{Lat}})$$

if flying with the vertical side of image (V_f) parallel to the flying direction.

During the flight an adequate number of points has to be surveyed (positioned) to support the consequent step of Image Bundle Adjustment. GCPs can correspond to stable and proper objects present at the ground (e.g. walls corner, poles, etc.) or coded panels have to be preventively positioned over the area to be surveyed and their 3D position determined (in general by RTK/PPK GNSS survey)

During the flight some **Ground Control Points** must be positioned (panels) and surveyed, possibly by a Geodetic GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) operating in RTK (Real Time Kinematic) or PPK (Post Processing Kinematic) mode → 3D positioning precision is about 2 cm.

GCP are required to solve image BUNDLE ADJUSTMENT (image orientation) in support (or completely alternative) of direct measurements from GNSS and IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) that, in general, UAV are equipped with. With a sufficient number of pre-signalized GCP, GNSS/IMU measurements can be avoided at all.

Panels can be also used to calibrate (radiometrically) sensor measures

IMAGE ORIENTATION (also named Block Bundle Adjustment) is MANDATORY to solve a photogrammetric survey. This operation is in charge of computing/estimating, for all images, the correspondent Exterior Orientation (EO) parameters (6), i.e. to virtually place images where they were at the time of the acquisition. EO parameters are different for all the images of the block and can be divided in POSITION and ATTITUDE parameters.

a) EO POSITION parameters are X_0, Y_0, Z_0 coordinates of the focal point when the image was acquired;

b) EO ATTITUDE parameters are ω, ϕ, κ (pitch), γ (yaw) angles defining the rotation of the image system in respect of the cartographic reference frame.

During image orientation the image coordinate system (ξ, η, ζ) is aligned to the object/cartographic one (X, Y, Z), translated and scaled.

The INTERIOR ORIENTATION of a block is the operation aimed at recovering the value of the IO parameters, i.e. these technical features of the camera/sensor that are needed to solve the collinearity equations:

1. Calibrated focal length, c , of the camera/sensor;
2. Principal Point coordinates in the image space (S_{pp}, η_{pp});
3. Radial-tangential distortion coefficients.

IO parameters are equal for all the images (depending on camera/sensor) and permits to describe the path of the projecting rays relating focal point to image points within the camera. All measures done in the image space refer to the physical center of the image called FIDUCIAL POINT (CF). Unfortunately, the optical axis of the system (central projecting ray) never intersects the focal plane in correspondence of FC, but in a different point called PRINCIPAL POINT (PP) whose position must be known with respect to FC. A little shift of PP from CF determines a positioning error, in the object space, whose amount can be obtained by multiplying the shift per the image scale factor. NOT NEGLIGIBLE!

The equations describing the central perspective geometry are named EQUATIONS OF COLLINEARITY (CE). They can operate UPWARD (from ground XYZ to image $\xi\eta$) and DOWNWARD (from image $\xi\eta$ to ground XYZ). The coefficients of the perspective model are represented by the above mentioned EO (in red) and IO (in green) parameters.

$$\xi = \xi_0 - c \frac{r_{11}(X - X_0) + r_{21}(Y - Y_0) + r_{31}(Z - Z_0)}{r_{13}(X - X_0) + r_{23}(Y - Y_0) + r_{33}(Z - Z_0)} + \Delta\xi(\rho)$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 - c \frac{r_{12}(X - X_0) + r_{22}(Y - Y_0) + r_{32}(Z - Z_0)}{r_{13}(X - X_0) + r_{23}(Y - Y_0) + r_{33}(Z - Z_0)} + \Delta\eta(\rho)$$

- X_0, Y_0, Z_0 are the POSITION parameters of the EXTERIOR ORIENTATION
- r_i = elements of a rotation matrix needed to align image plane to the object reference system. They contain the ATTITUDE parameters of the EXTERIOR ORIENTATION (ω, ϕ, κ)
- $\Delta\xi(\rho), \Delta\eta(\rho)$ radial distortion terms

Bundle Adjustment is aimed at providing an estimate for all the unknowns (EO parameters) by operating a Least Squares solution of a highly redundant numerical system made of a sufficient number of (collinearity) equations. During the estimation IO parameters can be entered the estimation process as additional unknowns to refine their nominal values.

In modern acquisition systems EO parameters can be directly measured (on board of the RPAS/airplane) coupling a GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). The GNSS receiver is in charge of measuring the position of the focal point (X_0, Y_0, Z_0); the IMU (gyroscopes + accelerometers) is in charge of measuring attitude angles. Position and attitude measures have to be synchronized with image shots. If images EO is obtained with reference to the measured data, the approach is named DIRECT GEOREFERENCING and no estimates is required.

In spite of this technologically advanced (but expensive) solution, it has been proved that the performances offered by these systems, especially as regards the inertial platform, operated with no support from Ground Control Points, determines worse orientation solutions than those obtainable by the traditional estimating method based on the numerical solution of an adequate number of collinearity equations built around GROUND CONTROL POINTS (GCPs) and TIE POINTS (TPs).

$$X = X_0 + (Z - Z_0) \frac{f_{11}(\xi - \xi_0) + f_{12}(\eta - \eta_0) - f_{13}c}{f_{31}(\xi - \xi_0) + f_{32}(\eta - \eta_0) - f_{33}c}$$

$$Y = Y_0 + (Z - Z_0) \frac{f_{21}(\xi - \xi_0) + f_{22}(\eta - \eta_0) - f_{23}c}{f_{31}(\xi - \xi_0) + f_{32}(\eta - \eta_0) - f_{33}c}$$

Downward equations are used during the restitution phase of the process, i.e. to measure 3D position of imaged points in the object space from an oriented image block. Software operate autonomously both recognition of homologous points on different images (within their overlapping area) and computation of correspondent XYZ coordinates. For each point to be measured, 2 equations can be written containing 3 UNKNOWNS (XYZ). Consequently at least 2 images are required (4 equations) to solve the position of the point in the object space. When operating restitution, both EO and ID parameters are known having been estimated in the previous step.

CE from two different "oriented images" referring to the same object point are used to triangulate and get an estimate of its XYZ coordinates. Since the number of equations (2*2=4) is greater than the number of unknowns (XYZ), an estimate of precision of measured coordinates (in the image space) can be given, too.

$$X = f_1(\xi_1, \eta_1, Z, P_i)$$

$$Y = f_2(\xi_1, \eta_1, Z, P_i)$$

$$X = f_3(\xi_2, \eta_2, Z, P_i)$$

$$Y = f_4(\xi_2, \eta_2, Z, P_i)$$

UAV data processing: from images to measures Spectral ISSUES

AAAGRI - Brasov, 8-14 May 2024

Borgogno Mondino, Enrico
DISAFA - University of Torino

The atmosphere is an important player in remote sensing. It plays a double role depending on its transmittance and scattering properties. A) Sun light is attenuated both while reaching (irradiance) and leaving (radiance) the ground. Atmosphere transmits differently the different wavelengths of light; B) atmosphere scatters light in all directions, included towards the sensor and down to the ground.

Scattering can be somehow considered the reflecting behaviour of the atmosphere

3 TYPES OF SCATTERING

SELECTIVE SCATTERING (RAYLEIGH) - Natural in clear sky conditions
Particles with dimensions $\ll \lambda$ (wavelength in the range we are interested in [400-2500 nm]) (atmospheric gases)

MIE SCATTERING - Man related activities
Particles with dimensions near to λ (dust and smoke in the low atmosphere)

NOT-SELECTIVE SCATTERING - Natural in cloudy conditions
Particles with dimensions $\gg \lambda$ (condensed water, clouds)

RAYLEIGH'S SELECTIVE SCATTERING: bands are scattered differently by the atmosphere. Scattering is active in the visible region of the spectrum, and turns to be negligible in the medium infrared region.

- Effects
- 1) Sky colour \rightarrow it depends on the optical path of the signal, therefore on the hour of the day
 - 2) Back-Scattering towards the sensor. It records both the atmospheric contribution and the surfaces contribution to the signal

Atmosphere is selective respect to signal wavelengths → it lowers signal intensity differently for the different bands. Those REGIONS of spectrum where atmosphere is transparent (transmittance near to 1) are called **ATMOSPHERIC WINDOWS**.

Sensors must necessarily operate in the atmospheric windows.

Atmospheric windows modify Sun irradiance availability at the ground.

Premises

- a) Raw images code Radiance, NOT Reflectance
- b) At-the-sensor recorded radiance is made of ground surface contribution + atmospheric scattering (noise)
- c) Atmosphere weakens both incoming and outgoing radiation (transmittance)

→ Raw multispectral images cannot be interpreted as a collection of spectral signatures

- L_{λ}^{atm} : atmospheric scattering
- $r(\lambda)$: at-the-ground surface reflectance
- L_{λ} : Sun Irradiance (TOA)
- τ_{λ} : atmospheric transmittance
- b : Sun incidence angle

The function relating surface reflectance to lighting conditions and at-the-sensor recorded radiance (L_{λ}) is called **RADIATIVE TRANSFER MODEL (RTM)**.

- π takes into account the Lambertian behaviour of the surface. The incoming radiation, when reflected is diluted over an hemisphere ($\sim \pi$ steradians)
- k is the Earth-Sun distance factor in charge of tuning the reference Sun Irradiance (equinox) in respect of the date of acquisition
- \hat{L}_{λ}^{atm} is the scattering contribution of the atmosphere that has to be taken into consideration at the sensor (noise to be minimized) and at the ground (scattered light increases energy availability at the ground)
- τ_{λ} is the estimated transmittance at the moment of the acquisition (band dependent)

$$\rho_{\lambda}(x, y) = \frac{\pi \cdot [L_{\lambda}(x, y) - \hat{L}_{\lambda}^{atm}]}{\tau_{\lambda out} \cdot [k \cdot \sin[\beta(x, y)] \cdot E_{\lambda} + \hat{L}_{\lambda}^{atm} \cdot \pi]}$$

While dealing with public open data this problem can be easily overcome by selecting the proper Processing LEVEL for data (LEVEL 2 in general) that means **AT-THE GROUND REFLECTANCE CALIBRATED DATA and ORTHOPROJECTED** (in general in WGS 84 Geographic Coordinates, or WGS84 UTM Projected coordinates)

RAW DATA from sensors record **RADIANCE (Power flux)** and **NOT REFLECTANCE**. Consequently, they cannot be used as they come. A radiometric calibration of multispectral images is required.

HOW? → Different Approaches are possible

1. An opportunistic **RADIATIVE TRANSFER MODEL** can be applied. Many auxiliary infos are required concerning sensor technical features, atmosphere properties, scene lighting geometry

$$\rho_{\lambda} = \frac{\pi \cdot (R_{\lambda} - \hat{L}_{\lambda}^{atm})}{\tau_{\lambda out} \cdot [k \cdot \sin(\theta) \cdot E_{\lambda} + \hat{L}_{\lambda}^{atm} \cdot \pi]}$$

2. **EMPIRICAL LINE** (an empirical regressive model must be calibrated with reference to some spectral measures from ground campaigns). The assumption is that the Radiative Transfer model can be reduced to a linear relationship linking calibrated ground measures with Digital numbers

$$\rho_{\lambda} = \alpha_{\lambda y} \cdot DN_{\lambda} + \beta_{\lambda y}$$

Sampled spectral signatures (as recorded by sensors) are discrete approximations of the real ones. Higher is the spectral resolution of images, higher is the consistency between real and observed spectral signatures.

But we don't start from reflectance, but from DN. How to do it?

The first step is to convert DN into correspondent radiance values is Image Calibration. DN are related to correspondent radiance value by a CALIBRATION FUNCTION.

- Each detector has a specific calibration function
- The calibration function defines the relationship between DN and correspondent Radiance values
- Each band refers to different detectors, therefore bands have different calibration functions.

INCIDENCE ANGLE MAP ← DSM (Digital Surface Model)

GIS ordinary tools (topographic/lighting) can be used to derive a map of the incidence angle with a resolution consistent with the one of the input DSM. In agriculture, at field level, the DSM from the point cloud can provide such an input.

Transmittance and Scattering can be estimated:

- By rigorous physically-based approaches, where atmosphere is modelled, as it was at the acquisition time; well known models operating in this way are ATCOR3/4, FLAASH, MODTRAN.
- By empirical approaches based on strong simplifications, but effective enough for the most of applications (NOT for studies concerning water or snow analysis). In general, this approach adopts: a) some reference values for transmittance from literature (basically suggested for different latitudes and landscapes); b) simplified strategies for scattering estimation, in general operating in DOS (dark object subtraction) mode.

Transmittance (τ)

Reference transmittance values are reported for summer mid-latitude areas with clear sky (Landsat 8 OLI bands).

Often these reference values are locally tuned in respect of pixel geographic position (both planimetric and altimetric), since transmittance effect strictly depends on light rays optical path (thickness of atmosphere that radiation goes through).

Bande L8 OLI	τ
1	0.50
2	0.60
3	0.65
4	0.65
5	0.80
6	0.89
7	0.92

Scattering (\hat{L}_λ^{atm}): DOS approach

Intensity of scattering (depending on band) is performed according to the following hypotheses:

- Shadow areas should not reflect other than scattered component of light;
- Shadow areas can be found where radiance is minimum;
- Scattered radiance is the same for the whole scene to calibrate (true only for limited and flat areas)

Scattering (\hat{L}_λ^{atm}): DOS approach

The intensity of the atmosphere scattered light is expected to be different for each band and possibly decreasing while wavelengths increase (according to Rayleigh's Law). Its estimation can be achieved in different ways. Here, the proposed DOS approach is based on the band (radiance calibrated) histogram analysis. We assume as an estimate of scattering intensity the radiance value (X axis) preceding the steep left slope trait of the histogram (red arrow).

IRRADIANCE VALUES at the top of the atmosphere can be estimated once known Sun EXITANCE (from Planck's Law) and a seasonal coefficient (SF, k or d) able to tune up this value according to the instantaneous distance between Sun and Earth. Since bands, that sensors can record, correspond to ranges of wavelengths the EXITANCE curve from Planck's Law has to be integrated within these ranges. An example is given for Landsat 8 OLI and Sentinel 2 MSI sensors.

band	Transmittance	IRR [W/m2]	Band center (micron)	band name
1	0.5	1913.57	0.443	Aerosol
2	0.6	1941.63	0.4905	Blue
3	0.65	1822.48	0.5695	Green
4	0.62	1513.79	0.665	red
5	0.8	1425.56	0.7095	NIR Red Edge 1
6	0.8	1388.32	0.7405	NIR Red Edge 2
7	0.8	1163.19	0.783	NIR Red Edge 3
8	0.8	1056.39	0.8425	NIR wide
8a	0.8	925.19	0.905	NIR Red Edge-4
9	0.4	813.04	1.945	Water/Vapour
10	0.95	387.15	1.375	CIrus
11	0.89	245.59	1.64	MIR1
12	0.92	85.25	2.13	MIR2

Sentinel 2 MSI

band	Transmittance	IRR [W/m2]	Band center (micron)	band name
1	0.5000	1955.11	0.443	Aerosol
2	0.6000	1969.08	0.483	Blue
3	0.6300	1864.87	0.5615	Green
4	0.6200	1559.92	0.6645	red
5	0.8014	1427.38	0.8014	NIR
6	0.8951	1427.56	1.6265	MIR1
7	0.9163	76.75	2.2005	MIR2

Landsat 8 OLI

How to become a GEDI Master using High-Resolution Lasers for Earth's Forest Monitoring

Mihai Daniel NITA

Training accessible at <https://sites.google.com/view/geditraining/>

Contents

1. Introduction (10 minutes)	2. GEDI Data Overview (15 minutes)	3. Pre-processing GEDI Data (20 minutes)	4. Integrating and Visualizing Data in GEE (30 minutes)	5. Applying Machine Learning (30 minutes)	6. Exporting and Using Data (15 minutes)	7. Q&A and Wrap-Up (20 minutes)
Overview of GEDI: Explain the Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) and its role in forest monitoring. Objectives: Highlight the main learning outcomes of the lecture.	Understanding GEDI Data: Quick overview of data characteristics including the laser system and data footprint. Accessing GEDI and Google Earth Engine (GEE): Instructions on accessing these platforms.	Data Preparation: Demonstrate key steps to clean and prepare data for GEE. Practical Exercise: Quick hands-on practice on sample data (demonstration-based due to time constraints).	GEE Basics: Brief intro to GEE and its capabilities. Loading and Visualizing Data: Step-by-step demonstration of how to load and visualize GEDI data in GEE. Short Exercise: Participants follow along to load their sample data.	Machine Learning Overview: Introduce essential machine learning concepts related to forest characteristics prediction. Model Implementation in GEE: Guide through applying a simple machine learning model to the GEDI data. Interactive Demonstration: Showcase a pre-built model run.	Exporting GeoTIFF Files: Instruction on how to export data from GEE. QGIS Introduction: Brief demo on importing and viewing GeoTIFF files in QGIS.	Q&A Session: Address participant questions and discuss common challenges. Summary and Further Resources: Provide a recap and additional resources for further learning.

1. Introduction

- Why monitoring Forests?

1. Introduction

- How to monitor changes in Forests by combining active (GEDI Laser Measurements) and passive sensors (Sentinel 2) to create wall-to-wall maps with canopy height

1. Overview of GEDI

- Overview of GEDI

1. Overview of GEDI

- GEDI contains three Nd:YAG lasers, emitting 1064 nm light. These pulse 242 times per second with a power of 10 mJ, firing short pulses of light (14 ns long) down towards the Earth's surface with a beam divergence of 56 mrad, resulting in footprints averaging 25 m in diameter.

1. Overview of GEDI

1. Overview of GEE

- Overview of GEE

2. GEDI Data Overview

- Understanding GEDI Data: Quick overview of data characteristics including the laser system and data footprint.
- Accessing GEDI and Google Earth Engine (GEE): Instructions on accessing these platforms.

3. Pre-processing GEDI Data

- Data Preparation: Demonstrate key steps to clean and prepare data for GEE.
- Practical Exercise: Quick hands-on practice on sample data (demonstration-based due to time constraints).

4. Integrating and Visualizing Data in GEE

- GEE Basics: Brief intro to GEE and its capabilities.
- Loading and Visualizing Data: Step-by-step demonstration of how to load and visualize GEDI data in GEE.
- Short Exercise: Participants follow along to load their sample data.

5. Applying Machine Learning

- Machine Learning Overview: Introduce essential machine learning concepts related to forest characteristics prediction.
- Model Implementation in GEE: Guide through applying a simple machine learning model to the GEDI data.
- Interactive Demonstration: Showcase a pre-built model run.

6. Exporting and Using Data

- Exporting GeoTiff Files: Instruction on how to export data from GEE.
- QGIS Introduction: Brief demo on importing and viewing GeoTiff files in QGIS.

7. Q&A and Wrap-Up

- Q&A Session: Address participant questions and discuss common challenges.
- Summary and Further Resources: Provide a recap and additional resources for further learning.

Digital Transformation in Agriculture

M. Ivanovici*

AI4AGRI Summer School
Brașov, România
8-14 May 2024

* based on the chapter: M. Ivanovici, Gh. Oltean, C. Florea, R. Coliban, M. Ștefan, K. Marandskiy, Chapter 25. Digital Transformation in Agriculture, Digital Transformation, Springer, 2024, in press.

Context

- Remote sensing → new possibilities for monitoring Earth
- Earth Observation (EO) data – peta bytes of data daily
- Digital data from in-site, proximal or satellite level measurement transformed agriculture in the last decades
 - temperature, wind, soil roughness or humidity, water and chlorophyll level content, albedo, complemented by multi- or hyper-spectral and Synthetic-Aperture RADAR (SAR) imagery create a Big Data context in agriculture
 - is fostered in precision agriculture and crop management

The ultimate goal

- The goal is twofold:
 - to monitor the evolution (vegetation status) of the plants
 - Early detection of plant stress or any disease
 - to estimate yield
- EO-based applications include cartography of agricultural land and grassland, crop identification and monitoring, stress and disease early detection, animal inventory, biomass estimation from grasslands etc

Agriculture 5.0

- Agriculture 5.0 fosters the latest cutting-edge technologies from Artificial Intelligence (AI) → smart agriculture
- applications of AI for crop management in Agriculture 5.0:
 - automatic determination of site-specific crop requirements in terms of water and nutrients,
 - elaboration of farming strategies regarding the control of chemical and mechanical treatments,
 - yield and price estimation by deploying AI-based intelligent decision support systems and,
 - future use of agri-robots for sowing and harvesting.

A Historical Perspective

Digitalization in Agriculture

- In the context of precision agriculture, measuring a parameter related to the plant – either its geometric, physical or chemical properties

—measurement→ 42

Associating a digital number to a plant through a measuring process (*42 alludes to the response of the Deep Thought supercomputer in the book „The Hitchhiker’s Guide to Galaxy” by D. Adams).

One number

- chlorophyll level,
 - sugar content of tubers and related parameters (NO₃ – glucose, K, Ca²⁺, Na⁺, pH),
 - anthocyanin, CO₂ and H₂O flux in photosynthesis process and
 - related parameters (temperature, stomatal conductance, transpiration rate), etc
- *Invasive or non-invasive?*

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Practicle example for sugar beet

healthy stressed

Sugar beet crop in-situ RGB digital images

	Chl a	Chl b	NDVI	WI	SR	MSR	ND
crop A (stressed)	0.75	0.83	0.81	1.23	9.28	4.46	0.56
crop B (healthy)	0.79	0.87	0.84	1.24	11.75	5.01	0.60

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Vegetation Indices (VIs)

- can reveal useful information about the plant status
- VIs are extensively used to assess and monitor the vegetation and health status of the agricultural crops
- the most commonly used are the Normalized Difference of Vegetation Index (NDVI) or Leaf Area Index (LAI)

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$$

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NDVI Explained

- NDVI ∈ (0.66, 1] indicates healthy and dense canopy
- NDVI ∈ (0.33, 0.66] indicates moderate healthy or stressed vegetation
- NDVI ∈ (0, 0.33] corresponds to unhealthy vegetation, underdeveloped canopy or not cultivated regions, and
- NDVI ∈ [-1, 0] to dead vegetation (water surfaces, artificial materials or lack of vegetation)

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Many VIs do exist!

- **Broadband greenness:**
 - Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI),
 - Difference Vegetation Index (DVI),
 - Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI),
 - Global Environmental Monitoring Index (GEMI),
 - Green Atmospherically Resistant Index (GARI),
 - Green Difference Vegetation Index (GDVI),
 - Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI),
 - Green Ratio Vegetation Index (GRVI),
 - Green Vegetation Index (GVI),
 - Infrared Percentage Vegetation Index (IPVI),
 - Leaf Area Index (LAI),
- **Broadband greenness:**
 - Modified Non-Linear Index (MNL),
 - Modified Simple Ratio (MSR),
 - Non-Linear Index (NLI),
 - Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI),
 - Optimized Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (OSAVI),
 - Renormalized Difference Vegetation Index (RDVI),
 - Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI),
 - Simple Ratio (SR),
 - Sum Green Index (SGI),
 - Transformed Difference Vegetation Index (TDVI),
 - Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index (VARI),
 - WorldView Improved Vegetative Index (WV-VI).

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More VIs

- **Narrowband Greenness:**
 - Modified Chlorophyll Absorption Ratio Index (MCARI),
 - Modified Chlorophyll Absorption Ratio Index Improved (MCARI2),
 - Modified Red Edge Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (MRENDVI),
 - Modified Red Edge Simple Ratio (MRESR),
 - Modified Triangular Vegetation Index (MTVI),
 - Modified Triangular Vegetation Index – Improved (MTVI2),
 - Red Edge Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (RENDVI),
 - Red Edge Position Index (REPI),
 - Transformed Chlorophyll Absorption Reflectance Index (TCARI),
 - Triangular Vegetation Index (TVI),
 - Vogelmann Red Edge Index 1 (VREI1) and 2 (VREI2).

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And more...

- **Canopy nitrogen:**
 - Normalized Difference Nitrogen Index (NDNI).
- **Canopy Water Content:**
 - Moisture Stress Index (MSI),
 - Normalized Difference Infrared Index (NDII),
 - Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI),
 - Normalized Multi-band Drought Index (NMDI),
 - Water Band Index (WBI).
- **Dry or Senescent Carbon:**
 - Normalized Difference Lignin Index (NDLI),
 - Cellulose Absorption Index (CAI),
 - Plant Senescence Reflectance Index (PSRI).

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And, finally!

- **Leaf Pigments:**
 - Anthocyanin Reflectance Index 1 (ARI1) and 2 (ARI2),
 - Carotenoid Reflectance Index 1 (CRI1) and 2 (CRI2).
- **Light Use Efficiency:**
 - Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI),
 - Structure Insensitive Pigment Index (SIPI),
 - Red Green Ratio Index (RGR).

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Vector spectral measurements

- All the VIs are computed based on specific wavelengths in the visible and/or infra-red domain
- Sometimes the full spectral information is preferred
- The measured parameter can be a vector,
 - **multi-spectral** (e.g. 9 reflectance values on various wavelengths for LANDSAT 8 satellite, 13 for Sentinel 2 satellite, 16 for the Crop Scan spectrophotometer) or
 - **hyper-spectral** (tens or even hundreds of wavelengths).

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Multispectral crop measurements

- Spectral reflectance curves for the two sugar beet crops previously analyzed
- CropScan measurements
- Between 460nm and 1500nm
- Lower IR response for stressed plants

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Next step – more plants

→remote sensing→ 42

Associating a digital number to a number of plants through **remote sensing**

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One more step - imaging

- Averaging a measurement over a given area can be irrelevant
- Thus, we associate a matrix of measurements values

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Pixel model

- physical and mathematical model of pixel value formation in a CMOS imaging sensor

- n_p - number of incident photons,
- η - pixel's effective quantum,
- n_e - number of electrons,
- n_d - characteristic noise of the sensor (dark current),
- K - amplification,
- Q - quantization process, quantization noise with dispersion σ_q ,
- y - numerical value of the pixel

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1, 3, infinity

- Every pixel in the sensor is sensitive to a wide spectrum of light, from visible (approximately 400 to 800 nm) and the infra-red (approximately 800 to 1500nm)
- Practically all imaging sensors are intrinsically panchromatic

Bayer format (left) for color imaging and mosaic (right) for multispectral image acquisition (inspired from Silios, France)

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Bayer mosaic – bio-inspired

Spectral sensitivity (cones)

Color pixel formation using Bayer filter mosaic

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Bayer mosaic types

From left to right: GRBG, GBRG, BGGR and RGGB

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Demosaicing. An example

GRGB Bayer filter for a 14x14 pixels CMOS sensor

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Multispectral imaging using mosaic

- Example (after SILIOS, France)

spectral sensitivity curves (ideal)

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Spectrophotometry – solution for infty

- Isaac Newton diffraction
- spectral sensitivity curves (color references)

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Hyperspectral imaging

- Illustration of the four types of spectral image acquisition systems

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Evolution of spectral resolution

- Spectral resolution: 1, 3, tens, hundreds...

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Example of NDVI map

- NDVI color palette:
- a) Sentinel-2 specific
- b) Contrasting palette
- c) Four-color palette

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Big Data from Space

- 3V Concept: volume, velocity and variety
 - 4V, 5V: value, variability, virtuality etc.
- Optical / RADAR / thermal data – PB of data per day!
- Various Space programs and missions
- Copernicus – Sentinel-2 – for agriculture

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Sentinel-2 MSI

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Sentinel-2 data

- Sentinel-2 RGB images of the Brasov area, Romania from six consecutive months (from February to July 2023)

Sentinel-1 images

- SAR images from Sentinel-1A as RGB composites sensed in April 2023, VV, VH and VV/VH gray-scale images

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Smart Agriculture or Agriculture 5.0

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Widely-used AI models

- Random Forest (RF)
- Support Vector Machines (SVM)
- Neural Networks (NN)
- Gradient Boosting Machine (derived from AdaBoost)
- Deep Convolutional Networks – Deep Learning DL (e.g. AlexNet)

Comparison between classical and DL

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The Earth Digital Twin

inspired from https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/Destination_Earth

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Applications

- NDVI time series for crop monitoring

Sentinel-2 NDVI images of the same scene (Brasov city area, Romania) from six consecutive months (February-July 2023), visualized with MERIS VI color scheme

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Crop identification based on NDVI profile

Inspired from ECA - European Court of Auditors, Special report: Using new imaging technologies to monitor the Common Agricultural Policy: steady progress overall, but slower for climate and environment monitoring, 2020

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AI-based object detection

- weed detection (left) and animal detection (right) in UAV-acquired images in the visible spectrum – using YOLO

Sasidharan T. S., Latini D., Ivanovici M., Schiavon G., Thangavel K., Del Frate F., Smart Weed Control: Real-Time Inference and On-board Data Processing using Edge-AI, EARSeL Symposium, Bucharest, Romania, 3-6 July 2023

Illustration of object detection on an UAV-acquired image provided by Smart Intuitive Drones SRL, Simaia, Romania

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Lecturers' biographies

Prof. Josiane Mothe is full professor in computer science since 2002 at the CNRS IRIT lab. She is a specialist in information retrieval, data mining, big data and applied machine learning. She obtained accreditation to direct research in 2000 and 20 PhD students were or still are under her supervision. From 2012 to 2015, she led the Information Retrieval – Exploration and visualization team of the IRIT lab. She was responsible for the ANR CAAS project which ended in 2014, and participated to 3 FP7 projects. She was the scientific manager for UPS-IRIT in the FREMIT federation until 2013. Since 2020, she has been the co-publisher of the ACM SIGIR-Forum journal, after holding the editor-in-chief position for Europe and Africa at the Information Retrieval Journal, Springer (2004-2014). She acted as co-chair for CLEF 2015 and as program committee chair for CORIA 2018, CLEF 2018, ECIR 2020 (short papers). She is a program committee member of the leading national and international conference on that field (SIGIR, CIKM, ECIR, CORIA). She led the FabSpace 2.0 (2016-19) H2020 European project which gathered 15 partners and the InnEO Space PhD project (dec 2020-23) H2020 which gathered 5 European partners, and she also participates in the UNIVERSEH, Erasmus+ project (2020-2023).

Prof. Fabio Del Frate is Full Professor at University of Rome "Tor Vergata" since 1999, where he is currently a Full Professor, teaching courses on Remote Sensing and Applied Electromagnetism in various Master and PhD Programs. He is the Coordinator of the "Design, Application, Regulation of UAVs" MSc program and Erasmus coordinator for the Engineering Macroarea. He is, or has been, principal investigator/project manager in several ESA and Italian Space Agency (ASI) funded research projects, author of more than 200 international scientific publications with a special focus on feature extraction algorithms from EO data using neural networks. He has been session organizer and in technical boards of International Conferences and Workshops focused on Geoscience and Remote Sensing. He has been Associate Editor for Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, Guest Editor for EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing and Remote Sensing. Currently he is a Member of the scientific section board of the Remote Sensing journal and Associate Editor for Frontiers of Remote Sensing. He has been a member of the ESA GOME ozone profile retrieval working group. In 2006 and 2007 he was a member of the group winning the IEEE data fusion contest. In 2015 he was appointed EUMETSAT Associate Scientist for activities regarding the estimation of precipitation rate from satellite data. From 2019 to 2022 he received an appointment by ESA as Visiting Professor at the ESA ESRIN centre to provide support in the use of AI for EO data processing. In 2006 he co-founded GEO-K srl, the 1st spin-off company of the University of "Tor Vergata".

Enrico Borgogno Mondino is Full Professor in Geomatics at the Dept. of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, University of Torino. His main research topics concern agro/forestry applications of Geomatics, included optical and SAR satellite, airborne and UAV remote sensing, digital photogrammetry, LiDAR, GIS and survey. Author of more than 150 papers in National and International Scientific Proceedings, Journals and Books. President of the Italian Association of Remote Sensing. President of the ASITA Scientific Committee. Vice-President of the Italian Confederation of Scientific Associations for Territorial and Environmental Information. Chair of the Agriculture Special Interest Group

of the European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories EARSeL. He is/has been scientific responsible of various national and international research projects. He is Editorial board member in MDPI Remote Sensing, MDPI Agronomy, MDPI Geomatics and has been Guest editor of Special Issues in the European Journal of Remote Sensing, MDPI Land, MDPI Remote Sensing, Frontiers in Forests and Global Change.

Yajing Yan received Ph.D. degree in geosciences and environment from the Laboratoire d'Informatique, Systèmes, Traitement de l'Information et de la Connaissance (LISTIC) and the Institut des Sciences de la Terre (ISTerre), Université Savoie Mont Blanc, Annecy-le-Vieux, France, in 2011. She was a Post-Doctoral Fellow with the Institut d'Électronique et des Télécommunications de Rennes, France, from January 2012 to June 2012, and with the Geo-Hydrodynamics and Environment Research group, University of Liège, Liège, Belgium, from July 2012 to August 2014. Since September 2014, she has been an Associate Professor with LISTIC, Université Savoie Mont Blanc. Her research interests include multitemporal interferometric synthetic aperture radar (InSAR) processing, data fusion, data assimilation and ML.

Behnood Rasti (Senior Member, IEEE) received Ph.D. degree in electrical and computer engineering from the University of Iceland, Reykjavik, Iceland, in 2014. In 2015 and 2016, he worked as a Post-Doctoral Researcher with the Electrical and Computer Engineering Department, University of Iceland. From 2016 to 2019, he was a Lecturer with the Center of Engineering Technology and Applied Sciences, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Iceland. He is currently a Principal Research Associate with Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Helmholtz Institute Freiberg for Resource Technology, Freiberg, Germany. His research interests include signal and image processing, machine/deep learning, remote sensing, and AI. Dr. Rasti was a Humboldt Research Fellow in 2020 and 2021. He won the Doctoral Grant of the University of Iceland Research Fund "The Eimskip University Fund" and the "Alexander von Humboldt Research Fellowship Grant" in 2013 and 2019, respectively. He serves as an Associate Editor for the IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters.

Nathalie Neptune got her Ph.D. degree in Computer Science from Université Toulouse III, Paul Sabatier, in Toulouse, France. Her PhD thesis topic was on big data and geo data for sustainable development, spatial thinking and visualization. She was a Schlumberger Foundation Faculty for the Future fellow from 2017 to 2020. During her PhD, she proposed a novel method to annotate satellite images showing changes in forests with words extracted from scientific publications with the proof of concept developed using Python and PyTorch. Her research interests include multimodal data mining using deep learning approaches for environmental phenomena detection and monitoring.

Corneliu Florea, after a stint with digital still camera software industry, he is currently a Full Professor at the Politehnia University of Bucharest, Romania, within Image Processing and Analysis group. There he lectures on machine learning, statistical signal and computer vision. His research interests include statistical approaches to machine learning and computer vision with a focus on non-supervised learning. He is author of more than 80 peer-reviewed papers and of more than 25 US patents.

Professor Mihai Nita is a Full Professor in the Department of Forest Engineering, Transilvania University of Brasov, specializing in Remote Sensing, GIS, Watershed Management and Hydrotechnical Structures. His research is centered on forest management and monitoring, leveraging expertise in RS-GIS for LULUCF applications, drone mapping, and Forest Ecosystem Services evaluation. Prof. Nita's career encompasses a broad spectrum of expertise in forestry, environmental management, and sustainable resource utilization. He has significantly contributed to various projects and research endeavors, enhancing the understanding and conservation of natural environments. His work spans forest management, geospatial analysis, environmental policy development, sustainable resource utilization, and extensive international collaboration.

Radu-Mihai Coliban is an Assistant Professor, holding a PhD degree from Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania in electronics (2017). His PhD thesis was entitled „Data acquisition and nonlinear processing – applications in imaging and complex experiments in physics“. He is a regular member of IEEE. His research interests include multivariate image processing and analysis (including color, multi-spectral and hyper-spectral), remotely-sensed satellite image analysis, data acquisition and processing, data fusion, digital hardware design, FPGA programming and ASIC design.

Prof. Mihai Ivanovici holds a PhD in electronics from Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania. He is a full professor and has 15 years of experience in managing various research projects (funded by EU structural funds and the Romanian government, the Ministry of Education and Research or by Romanian private companies) and participating as researcher in national and international research projects (e.g. The ATLAS Experiment at LHC). He is head of MIV Laboratory, within Department of Electronics and Computers, Transilvania University of Braşov, România and member of the IEEE Signal Processing and IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing societies. He is a member of the Reviewers Board for MDPI Remote Sensing journal. His research interest and expertise are in the field of colour, multispectral and hyperspectral image processing and analysis. He is supervising PhD in the field of electronics, telecommunications and information technologies.